

Opportunities and Challenges of E-Commerce

The Case of Ethiopia

A PROJECT REPORT

Under the guidance of

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*in partial fulfillment of the requirement
for the award of the degree*

Of

MBA

IN

Information Systems

**SRI SAI Learning center – Code 02540
Addis Ababa**

April, 2011

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Student Declaration

I hereby declare that the project report entitled **Opportunities and Challenges of E-Commerce the Case of Ethiopia** Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Business Administration of Sikkim Manipal University, INDIA, is my original work and not submitted from the award of any other degree, diploma, fellowship, or any other similar title or prizes.

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List of Acronyms/Abbreviations:

ACH:	Automatic Clearing House
ATM:	Automatic Tailoring Machine
ATS:	Automatic Transfer System
B2B:	Business to Business
B2C:	Business to Customer
B2G:	Business to Government
C2C:	Customer to Customer
COMESA:	Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa
CRM:	Customer Relationship Management
ECX:	Ethiopian Commodity Exchange
EDE:	Electronic Data Exchange
EDI:	Electronic Data Interchange
EICTDA	Ethiopian Information Communication Technology Development Agency
EPS:	Electronic Payment System
ETC:	Ethiopian Telecommunication Corporation
G2G:	Government to Government
GATS:	General Agreement on Trade in Services
GATT:	General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade
ICT:	Information Communication Technology
IDC:	International Data Corp
IP:	Internet Protocol
ISO:	International Standard Organization
ISP:	Internet Service Provider
NBE:	National Bank of Ethiopia
NGN:	Next Generation Network
NICI :	National Information and Communication Infrastructure

OECD:	organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PASDEP:	Plan for Accelerated and Sustainable Development to End Poverty
PC:	Personal Computer
PDA:	Personal Digital Assistants
POS:	Point of Sale
SADC:	Southern African Development Community
SCM:	Supply Chain Management
SDPRP:	Sustainable Development and Poverty Reduction Program
SMS:	Short Messaging Service
SWIFT:	Society for Worldwide Interbank Financial Telecommunication
TCP/IP:	Transmission Control Protocol/ Internet Protocol
TFP:	Total Factor Productivity
UNCITRAL:	United Nations Commission on International Trade Law
UNDP:	United Nations Development Program
UNECA:	United Nations Economic Commission for Africa
WTO:	World Trade Organization

Acknowledgement

Thanks be to God the almighty ‘Medhanealem’!

I would like to acknowledge all individuals and organizations I contacted for their readiness to assist and share information with me and for their valuable inputs into this project.

Special thanks to my Advisor, Dr. Jes, B. Sundar for guiding me throughout the project. I am heartily thankful to Dr. Bewketu Tadesse who has shared his knowledge of e-commerce with me. This has been of great encouragement and guidance. This project paper would not have been possible without the support of Emmanuel J.Chinyama who has helped me especially in editing the paper from the initial to the final level.

I offer my regards and blessings to all of those who have supported me in answering the questionnaires, participating in the interview, and providing the necessary materials for my desk review, Specially to CBE Ato Alexander and his friends, NBE, EICTDA specially Ato Zelalem and e-systems Africa.

During the completion of the project, Rotarian Seble Hailu has guided me in producing coherent paper which has smooth flow of ideas and hence I am able to finish well. Thank you, Seble!

Executive Summary

Electronic commerce, in a broad sense, is the use of computer networks to improve organizational performance, increasing profitability, gaining market share, improving customer service, and delivering service in speedy way. This paper tries to analyze the challenges and opportunities of e-commerce, including its components. In addition to the general analysis of e-commerce, the paper further gives a detailed analysis of e-commerce in the case of Ethiopia. To conduct this project descriptive method of research design was followed, the participants of data gathering were selected based on judgmental sampling method. E-commerce has tremendous opportunities, this project paper has seen economy wide efficiency gains, access to direct export, easier inventory management, integration found to be the major ones. Ethiopia will be also the beneficiary of the above mentioned opportunities in addition it will increase the knowledge and exposure of people towards new ideas and thoughts. Though it has many prospects it has also its own challenges, challenges categorized generally in the world and specific to Ethiopia. Security and privacy, perception of risk in e-services, legal and policy issues, lack of adequate skilled manpower, socio cultural issues, transportation and delivery system are general challenges in the world and most of it is applicable to African countries. In Ethiopia in addition to the above mentioned challenges, infant stage of telecommunication infrastructure and not having e-payment system are the major bottle necks. To overcome these challenges and resolve step by step, number of African countries is developing policy, legal system, and people's awareness towards ICT. In the case of Ethiopia policy, standards and legal issues have been studied in 2010 and action will be taken in few years time. In terms of telecommunication and banking some improvements are in progress.

Chapter I: Introduction

1.1. Background

Internet has created a new world beyond the real world—a “virtual network world” or “The sixth continent” as called by Lu Yongxiang, the academician of Chinese Academy of Science. Electronic commerce (e-Commerce) brought about by internet is one of the most significant scientific accomplishments. In business, the prosperous e-commerce technology gives rise to a revolution in the circulation system. It breaks the boundary of time and space, alters the trade pattern, improves the circulation of merchandise, capital and information, and makes enterprises have an edge over others as well by reducing the cost of production effectively. In short, e-commerce has enabled the traditional business to achieve greater, faster, better and more economical results (Qin Zheng (Ed), 2009).

The influence of the e-commerce goes beyond the business activity. It makes a profound impact on each aspect of human society, such as production and employment, government function, working talent, law systems, and education among others. It permeates into every profile: industries, logistics, finance, media, governments, enterprises, research organizations and even traditional agricultures.

The development of the e-commerce will influence and impact to a larger extent every aspect of our society with each passing day. A new economic revolution on the basis of digitalization and Internet has set in. E-commerce cannot only raise greatly productivity, efficiency of economic operations, lower the economy operation cost, and make many originally impossible things possible, but also influence people’s life styles and every social aspect and therefore change their world outlook and methodology.

In the case of Ethiopia it is very clear that e-commerce is in its infant stage. This is evident with only few websites available, resulting in few Ethiopian products being advertised through e-commerce. In addition the existing websites are not implementing the ideas of e-commerce fully due to a number of challenges. These include lack of telecom infrastructure, policy, standards and readiness.

This paper tries to analyze the challenges and opportunities of e-commerce in general and in the case of Ethiopia in particular. It will also provide policy suggestions based on the findings.

1.2. Problem Statement

Ethiopia is among the COMESA Members located in the horn of Africa. The current rapid growth of e-commerce over the world is also influencing Ethiopia.

Concerning e-commerce, there are no studies being conducted except very few handful of researches in related cases like challenges and issues of e-commerce, e-commerce readiness, e-payment, in Ethiopia. Due to the emergence of globalization, the number of Internet users is increasing all over the world. The nature of e-commerce by itself has its own motivating factor because of its 24/7 availability, no need of physical shops and no need or low cost of travel. Ethiopia is well known for exporting coffee, leather products, pulses and oil seeds, live animals and animal products, spices, food, civet, natural gum, agricultural products, cotton and cotton products, fish, textile, handmade cards and ornaments, honey and bees wax, shoes and aluminum scrap. This avails opportunities to be part of the international market through e-commerce.

This research addresses the following questions:

1. What is the role of e-commerce in the economic developments of in emerging globalization

2. What are the opportunities of e-commerce to the world, African countries and Ethiopia?
3. What are the challenges of e-commerce facing the world, African countries and Ethiopia?
4. What are the economic contributions of e-commerce to growth and development for Ethiopia?

1.3. General Objective

This paper tries is to analyze the challenges and opportunities of e-commerce in the world and with particular reference to Ethiopia.

1.4. Specific Objective

This research specifically:

- Analyzes the opportunities of e-commerce to the world economy.
- Examines the challenges of e-commerce to development.
- Explores the opportunities and challenges of e-commerce to Ethiopia
- Describes the economic contributions-commerce to growth and development for Ethiopia.

1.5. Significance of the Study Project

As stated above, there are very few researches conducted on e-commerce. Hence, this study will be helpful for policy makers, governmental and non-governmental organizations, as well as individuals who are involved in business to introduce e-commerce as a way to improve performance, increase efficiency and join the global market. It can also serve as a baseline for researchers to build on how to expand the service of e-commerce as the field is new-fangled. As this research will try to review the opportunities and challenges of e-

commerce in Ethiopia, it will serve as inputs for policy makers for it will strengthen the on-going growth and transformation plan of the Country's initiatives that are being undertaken jointly by the government, non-government and private organization

1.6. Scope and Limitations of the Project

There is no limitation to e-commerce as far as the entire necessary infrastructure and policy is available throughout the world. However, the scope of this paper is limited to the case of Ethiopian context, by which organizations that are directly related to e-commerce: ICT Agency, National Bank of Ethiopia, Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, and Telecommunication Corporation were selected. It is well documented that the field of e-commerce is young throughout the world and in the case of Ethiopia very few have got orientation towards the sector. It was not possible to find a large population data and literature regarding the case of Ethiopia.

1.7. Operational Definition

E-Commerce: is a term for any type of business consists of the buying and selling of products, services, or commercial transaction that involves the transfer of information across the Internet. It covers a range of different types of businesses, from consumer-based retail sites, through auction or music sites, to business exchanges trading goods and services between corporations.

E-Tailing: electronic retailing is the selling of retail goods on the Internet. It is the most common form of business-to-consumer (B2C) transaction.

M-Commerce: mobile commerce is the buying and selling of goods and services through wireless technology

E-Payment: is a system of financial exchange between buyers and sellers in the online environment that is facilitated by a digital financial instrument (such as encrypted credit card numbers, electronic checks, or digital cash) backed by a bank, an intermediary, or by legal tender.

Internet: is a worldwide system of computer networks - a network of networks in which users at any one computer can, if they have permission, get information from any other computer (and sometimes talk directly to users at other computers).

Chapter II: Literature Review

2.1. What is e-Commerce

Electronic commerce, in a broad sense, is the use of computer networks to improve organizational performance. Increasing profitability, gaining market share, improving customer service, and delivering products faster are some of the organizational performance gains brought about by. Electronic commerce is more than ordering goods from an on-line catalog. It involves all aspects of an organization's electronic interactions with its stakeholders, the people who determine the future of the organization. Thus, electronic commerce includes activities such as establishing a web page to support investor relations or communicating electronically with college students who are potential employees (Victor, 2003).

In brief, electronic commerce involves the use of information technology to enhance communications and transactions with in an organization's stakeholders. Such stakeholders include customers, suppliers, government regulators, financial institutions, managers, employees, and the public at large. It allows consumers to electronically exchange goods and services with no barriers of time or distance.

According to Zheng Qin et.al (2003), e-commerce can be defined as; various online commercial activities focusing on commodity exchanges by electronic means, internet in particular, by companies, factories, enterprises, industrial undertakings and consumers.

A large number of well-known organizations and corporations also have their own definitions on e-commerce. For example, International Standards Organization (ISO) defines e-commerce as: a general term for exchange of

information among enterprise and between enterprise and customers. The Global Information Infrastructure Committee defines it as the economic activities using electrical communications, with which people can purchase products, advertise goods and settle.

The following are definitions given by transnational corporations Intel, Band HP respectively.

Intel: E-commerce is an electronic market, electronic trade and electronic service.

IBM: E-commerce is an information technology web business.

HP: E-commerce is a way to accomplish commercial business by electronic means.

Since e-commerce is a brand new science, it is not at all surprising that there are various definitions about it. In addition, a premature uniform definition for e-commerce may slow the development of e-commerce. E-commerce shall be social, economic activities between social principal parts by taking advantages of computers and network (Qin Zheng (Ed), 2009).

Figure . The Development of E-Commerce from Electronic Data Exchange to E-Concept-Based

Source: Introduction to E-Commerce, 2009

To generalize all the above given definitions of e-commerce we can say that; Electronic commerce is a term for any type of business consists of the buying and selling of products or services, or commercial transaction that involves the

transfer of information across the Internet. It covers a range of different types of businesses, from consumer-based retail sites, through auction or music sites, to business exchanges trading goods and services between corporations. It is currently one of the most important aspects of the Internet to emerge.

Electronic commerce over the Internet is a new way of conducting business. Though young, it has the potential to radically alter economic activities and the social environment. Already, it affects such large sectors as communications, finance and retail trade. It holds promise in areas such as education, health and government. The largest effects may be associated not with many of the impacts that command the most attention (e.g. customized products, the elimination of middlemen) but with less visible, yet potentially more pervasive, effects on routine business activities (e.g. ordering office supplies, paying bills, and estimating demand), that is, on the way businesses interact.

As more and more countries use the Internet for trade, learning and social interaction, and as the number of industries affected by it grows strongly, it seems inevitable that the Internet's influence on international trade will grow very quickly. For instance US retail e-commerce revenue jumps from 94 billion USD in 2003 to 232.1 billion in 2008. International Data Corp (IDC) predicts an increase in Asia's percentage share in worldwide e-commerce revenue from 5 per cent in 2000 to 10 per cent in 2004.

2.2. Types of e-Commerce

The major types of e-commerce are: business-to-business (B2B); business to consumer (B2C); business-to-government (B2G); consumer-to-consumer (C2C) and government to government (G2G).

2.2.1 B2B e-Commerce

B2B e-commerce is simply defined as e-commerce between companies. This is the type of e-commerce that deals with relationships between and among businesses. About 80 per cent of e-commerce is of this type, and most experts predict that B2B e-commerce will continue to grow faster than the B2C segment.

The B2B market has two primary components: e-frastructure and e-markets. E-infrastructure is the architecture of B2B, primarily consisting of the following:

- logistics - transportation, warehousing and distribution (for example., Procter and Gamble);
- application service providers - deployment, hosting and management of packaged software from a central facility (for example., Oracle and Link share);
- outsourcing of functions in the process of e-commerce, such as Web-hosting, security and customer care solutions (for example., outsourcing providers such as eShare, NetSales, iXL Enterprises and Universal Access);
- auction solutions software for the operation and maintenance of real-time auctions in the Internet (for example., Moai Technologies and OpenSite Technologies);
- content management software for the facilitation of Web site content management and delivery (for example., Interwoven and ProcureNet); and
- Web-based commerce enablers (for example. Commerce One, a browser-based, enabled purchasing automation software).

E-markets are simply defined as Web sites where buyers and sellers interact with each other and conduct transactions. The common B2B examples and best

practice models are IBM, Hewlett Packard (HP), Cisco and Dell. Cisco, for instance, receives over 90per cent of its product orders over the Internet. Most B2B applications are in the areas of supplier management (especially purchase order processing), inventory management (for example. managing order-ship-bill cycles), distribution management (especially in the transmission of shipping documents), channel management (for example. information dissemination on changes in operational conditions), and payment management (for example. electronic payment systems or EPS). E-Marketer projects an increase in the share of B2B e-commerce in total global ecommerce from 79.2per cent in 2000 to 87per cent in 2004 and a consequent decrease in the share of B2C e-commerce from 20.8per cent in 2000 to only 13per cent in 2004.

Likewise, B2B growth is way ahead of B2C growth in the Asia-Pacific region. According to a 2001 *eMarketer* estimate, B2B revenues in the region are expected to exceed \$300 billion by 2004.

Table 1. Projected B2B E-Commerce by Region, 2000-2004 (*\$billions*)

	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	As a % of worldwide B2B commerce, 2004
North America	159.2	316.8	563.9	964.3	1,600.8	57.7
Asia/Pacific Rim	36.2	68.6	121.2	199.3	300.6	10.8
Europe	26.2	52.4	132.7	334.1	797.3	28.7
Latin America	2.9	7.9	17.4	33.6	58.4	2.1
Africa/Middle East	1.7	3.2	5.9	10.6	17.7	0.6
TOTAL	226.2	448.9	841.1	1,541.9	2,774.8	100.0

Source: wiki books

2.2.2 B2C e-Commerce

Business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce, is held between companies and consumers, and it involves customers gathering information; purchasing physical tangible goods like books or consumer products, or information goods such as electronic material or digitized content, software, e-books; and, for information goods, receiving products over an electronic network. It is the second largest and the earliest form of e-commerce. Its origins can be traced to online retailing (or e-tailing). Thus, the more common B2C business models are the online retailing companies such as Amazon.com, Drugstore.com, Beyond.com, Barnes and Noble and ToysRus. Other B2C examples involving information goods are E-Trade and Travelocity.

The common applications of this type of e-commerce is in the area of purchasing products and information, and personal finance management, which

pertain to the management of personal investments and finances with the use of online banking tools.

E-Marketer estimates that worldwide B2C e-commerce revenues will increase from US\$59.7 billion in 2000 to US\$428.1 billion by 2004. Online retailing transactions make up a significant share of this market.

B2C e-commerce reduces transactions costs (particularly search costs) by increasing consumer access to information and allowing consumers to find the most competitive price for a product or service. B2C e-commerce also reduces market entry barriers since the cost of putting up and maintaining a Web site is much cheaper than installing a “brick-and-mortar” structure for a firm (Zorayda, 2003)..

2.2.3 B2G e-commerce

Business-to-government (B2G) e-commerce is defined as commerce between companies and the public sector. It refers to the use of the Internet for public procurement, licensing procedures, and other government-related operations. This kind of e-commerce has two features: first, the public sector assumes a pilot/leading role in establishing e-commerce; and second, it is assumed that the public sector has the greatest need for making its procurement system more effective. Web-based purchasing policies increase the transparency of the procurement process (and reduce the risk of irregularities). To date, however, the size of the B2G e-commerce market as a component of total e-commerce is insignificant, as government e-procurement systems remain undeveloped (Zorayda, 2003).

2.2.4 C2C e-commerce

Consumer-to-consumer (C2C) e-commerce is simply commerce between private individuals or consumers. This type of e-commerce is characterized by the growth of electronic marketplaces and online auctions, particularly in vertical industries where firms/businesses can bid for what they want from among multiple suppliers. It perhaps has the greatest potential for developing new markets (Zorayda, 2003).

This type of e-commerce comes in at least three forms:

- auctions facilitated at a portal, such as eBay, which allows online real-time bidding on items being sold in the web;
- peer-to-peer systems, such as the Napster model (a protocol for sharing files between users used by chat forums similar to IRC) and other file exchange and later money exchange models; and
- Classified ads at portal sites such as Excite Classifieds and eWanted (an interactive, online marketplace where buyers and sellers can negotiate and which features “Buyer Leads & Want Ads”).

Consumer-to-business (C2B) transactions involve reverse auctions, which empower the consumer to drive transactions. A concrete example of this is when competing airlines gives a traveler best travel and ticket offers in response to the traveler’s post that she wants to fly from New York to San Francisco.

There is little information on the relative size of global C2C e-commerce. However, C2C figures of popular C2C sites such as eBay and Napster indicate that this market is quite large. These sites produce millions of dollars in sales every day (Zorayda, 2003).

2.2.5 G2G e-commerce

Governmental e-commerce requirements in social production and commercial activities can be divided into the following categories: participation, statistics, service, leading of production, circulation, consumption etc. Original national information system is mostly made up of national, provincial (municipal), local (municipal) organic statistics systems or multilevel statistics bureaus.

The statistics system is mainly aim at serving state-owned economy and enterprises with urban and rural survey teams attached to statistics bureaus as organizational guarantee to set up the foundation for macro decision making by collecting, processing, disposing data of industrial and agricultural production.

E-commerce of administrations is to carry out the administration, service and internal administration, among others. Effectively on computer network by making use of the ICT to establish an assembly of organic service systems between administrations, society and the public. In general, the targets of the e-government mainly are embodied in the following five aspects:

- i. Computerization, network and information of each government sector are beneficial to improve governmental efficiency, service and supervision. The e-government positively boosts the streamline of government organs and business simplification with the help of information technologies;
- ii. Administrations serve economy actively rather than passively, for which enterprises and citizens can have the knowledge of, and master governmental guideline and policies and services without the restriction of time and space;
- iii. Supply the public with excellent and diversified services by making use of network and information system built up by governments. The e-government supplies simple diversified services by making use of the

unified information resources and modern technology, such as voice and Internet;

- iv. Advance the whole social informatization by government. Display the application of the hi-tech to the community, enables the whole society to enjoy the facility of the information network, and practically boosts the social informatization; and

Create e-commerce supporting environments to suit the development of digital economy and to guide, layout and supervise e-commerce activities (Qin Zheng (Ed), 2009).

2.3. Other Online Businesses

2.3.1. M-Commerce

M-commerce (mobile commerce) is the buying and selling of goods and services through wireless technology. For example, hand held devices such as cellular telephones and personal digital assistants (PDAs). Japan is seen as a global leader in m-commerce.

As content delivery over wireless devices becomes faster, more secure, and scalable, some believe that m-commerce will surpass wireline e-commerce as the method of choice for digital commerce transactions. This may well be true for the Asia-Pacific where there are more mobile phone users than Internet users.

Sectors affected by m-commerce include:

- **Financial services**, including mobile banking (when customers use their handheld devices to access their accounts and pay their bills), as well as

brokerage services (in which stock quotes can be displayed and trading conducted from the same handheld device);

- **Telecommunications**, in which service changes, bill payment and account reviews can all be conducted from the same handheld device;
- **Service/retail**, as consumers are given the ability to place and pay for orders on-the-fly; and
- **Information services**, which include the delivery of entertainment, financial news, sports figures and traffic updates to a single mobile device. Forrester Research predicts US\$3.4 billion sales closed using PDA and cell phones by 2005.

Table 2.Forrester’s M-commerce Sales Predictions, 2001 - 2005

Device	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005
Sales closed on devices (in billions)					
PDA	0.0	0.1	0.5	1.4	3.1
Cell phone	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.3
Sales influenced by devices (in billions)					
PDA	1.0	5.6	14.4	20.7	24.0
Cell Phone	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.3	1.3

Source; wiki books

M-Commerce-Issues and Challenges were studied by Ravi T ET, al, 2003. They showed that the mobile Internet channel has opened up possibilities that business once dreamed of. There is a big gap between what the technology can do today and what the consumer has been led to expect. The good news is that the sources of consumer frustration like slow transmission speeds, difficult user interfaces and high costs - are being addressed by operators and equipment manufacturers. M-commerce players will need to move fast to improve the user interface and or innovative pricing structures. Despite the initial frustrations of

the early users, consumers envision that once many of the glitches are worked out, mobile applications will become an integral part of their daily lives.

Eighty-two percent of current and potential users think that the mobile device will become their personal travel assistant within the next three years. Eighty-one percent also foresee using these devices as part of their daily routine - for sending emails, getting news and information, and shopping. More than half (61 percent) expect these devices to become universal payment tools. Given this high level of consumer acceptance, the report predicts that by 2003, m-commerce will be where the Internet was in 1998 in terms of transaction value. In the B2C, total revenues generated by m-commerce will reach approximately \$100 billion, half of which will come from data transmission charges, e-mail subscription fees, and advertising; the other half will come from the value of transactions and related activities via mobile devices (wiki books.org).

2.3.2. E-tailing

E-tailing (or electronic retailing) is the selling of retail goods on the Internet. It is the most common form of business-to-consumer (B2C) transaction.

E-tailing has resulted in the development of e-tailware - software tools for creating online catalogs and managing the business connected with doing e-tailing. A new trend is the price comparison site that can quickly compare prices from a number of different e-tailers and link you to them (Zorayda, 2003).

2.3.3. Electronic Payment System

An electronic payment system (EPS) is a system of financial exchange between buyers and sellers in the online environment that is facilitated by a digital financial instrument (such as encrypted credit card numbers, electronic checks, or digital cash) backed by a bank, an intermediary, or by legal tender. EPS plays

an important role in e-commerce because it closes the e-commerce loop. In developing countries, the underdeveloped electronic payments system is a serious impediment to the growth of e-commerce. In these countries, entrepreneurs are not able to accept credit card payments over the Internet due to legal and business concerns. The primary issue is transaction security.

Wondwossen et.al, (2005) on their study on challenges and opportunities of e-payment in Ethiopia, wrote that many e-payment systems have emerged since the 1980s. However, major security, infrastructure, legal, regulatory and socio-cultural challenges have characterized the systems. Some regions and counties have made some commendable efforts to address the problems. For instance, the European Commission has developed a legal framework consisting directives to ensure free movement of online services, directives for the issuance of e-money and directives for e-signatures. The United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) formulated a model law on e-commerce in 1996. The SADC member countries developed the Southern African Development Community (SADC) Model Law on Electronic Transactions and Data Protection.

In Africa, e-payment is characterized by widespread challenges. Poor telecommunication infrastructure, limited readiness by banks, behavioral constraints, inadequate legal and regulatory framework, low level of credit card access are among the constraints that have hindered the progress of e-payment in Africa. However, it is to be underlined that there are some promising efforts in some African countries such as Egypt, Tunisia, and Morocco to lay a strong foundation for e-payment. These countries have committed huge resources towards ICT infrastructure, legal and regulatory framework for e-payment.

In Ethiopia, the study has found that e-commerce as well as its essential aspect e-payment is a recent phenomenon. However, the undergoing endeavor by some

banks and business enterprises to introduce and use e-payment is not to be undermined. As far as e-payment for bill payment is concerned except the success achieved by the Ethiopian Telecommunication Corporation by the introduction and wide use of prepaid cards for mobile bill payment, there is little progress by other companies despite a large potential demand in the country.

The major challenges of e-payment in Ethiopia include

- Poor telecommunication infrastructure
- Frequent power disruption
- People are resistant to new payment mechanisms
- Lack of skilled manpower
- Unavailability of payment laws, and regulations particularly for e-payment.

2.4. Components of E-Commerce Transaction Loop

E-commerce does not refer merely to firms putting up a web site for the purpose of selling goods to buyers over the Internet. For e-commerce to be a competitive alternative to traditional commercial transactions and for a firm to maximize the benefits of e-commerce, a number of technical as well as enabling issues have to be considered. A typical e-commerce transaction loop involves seller, transaction partner, consumer, policy maker (government), firm or business and Internet media.

The **Seller** should have the following components:

- A corporate web site with e-commerce capabilities (e.g., a secure transaction server);

- A corporate intranet so that orders are processed in an efficient manner; and
- IT-literate employees to manage the information flows and maintain the e-commerce system (Zorayda, 2003).

Transaction partners:

- Banking institutions that offer transaction clearing services (e.g., processing credit card payments and electronic fund transfers);
- National and international freight companies to enable the movement of physical goods within, around and out of the country.
- Authentication authority that serves as a trusted third party to ensure the integrity and security of transactions (Zorayda, 2003).

Consumers (in a business-to-consumer transaction):

- Form a critical mass of the population with access to the Internet and disposable income enabling widespread use of credit cards; and
- Possess a mindset for purchasing goods over the Internet rather than by physically inspecting items (Zorayda, 2003).

Firms/Businesses (in a business-to-business transaction):

- Form a critical mass of companies (especially within supply chains) with Internet access and the capability to place and take orders over the Internet (Zorayda, 2003).

Government:

- A legal framework governing e-commerce transactions (including electronic documents, signatures, and the like); and

- Legal institutions that would enforce the legal framework (i.e., laws and regulations) and protect consumers and businesses from fraud, among others (Zorayda, 2003).

The **Internet**, the successful use of which depends on the following:

- A robust and reliable Internet infrastructure; and
- A pricing structure that doesn't penalize consumers for spending time on and buying goods over the Internet (e.g., a flat monthly charge for both ISP access and local phone calls) (Zorayda, 2003).

Figure 1. Components of E-Commerce

Source: Introduction to E-Commerce, Zheng Qin, 2009

For e-commerce to grow, the above requisites and factors have to be in place. The least developed factor is an impediment to the increased uptake of e-commerce as a whole. For instance, a country with an excellent Internet infrastructure will not have high e-commerce figures if banks do not offer

support and fulfillment services to e-commerce transactions. In countries that have significant e-commerce figures, a positive feedback loop reinforces each of these factors.

Andrew D. Mitchell, *Towards Compatibility: The Future of Electronic Commerce within the Global Trading System*, Journal of Economic Law, 2001, Oxford University Press.

It highlights cracks in the wall between GATT and GATS and indicates that a re-conceptualization of the relationship between the agreements may be required in order to grapple better with the compatibility between electronic commerce and the WTO as currently structured. In order to move beyond these classifications difficulties, which have a real impact on economic choices made by traders, Members must seriously consider integrating GATT and GATS.

Even if GATS is amended according to the suggestions in this study there will be a problem in electronic commerce in the global trading system - the debilitating divide between the developed and developing countries in matters of electronic commerce. The divide presents a major impediment to realizing the full potential of electronic commerce for global trade. Therefore as long term goal, members should consider the view presented in this study that Electronic commerce is a form of global public good.

In addition, developing countries will need to educate their people on the benefits and technologies of electronic commerce.

A study by Arvind Panagariya (2000), states that the first set of issues discussed in the paper concerns the WTO discipline on this trade. Several points can be made in this context. First, all things considered, it will be most appropriate to classify e-commerce as trade in services with GATS discipline applied to it. Since this matter is still under negotiation, developing countries should be sure

that e-commerce is not classified as goods trade with a zero customs duty pact made permanent. Such an outcome would liberalize all e-commerce by default, undermining their bargaining power. Second, at present there is some disagreement about whether the Internet transactions in which the provider and recipient of a service are located in different countries should be classified as cross-border trade or consumption abroad. In making their commitments in the UR and post-UR negotiations in services, countries presumably viewed these transactions as cross-border trade. For if they are defined as consumption abroad, the category described as cross-border trade in services will be virtually vacuous. In view of this fact, it can be argued that the transactions under consideration be classified as cross-border trade. Third, in the area of intellectual property protection, developing countries must eventually confront the possibility of two WIPO treaties, concluded in December 1996 but yet to come into force, being brought into the WTO. These treaties have strong enforcement commitments that developing countries will need to study carefully.

Many of the countries may lack the ability to enforce and deliver the settlement of disputes in this area. Developing countries such as India that have the capacity to export skilled services through Internet should aggressively negotiate market access with developed countries in the forthcoming round. This involves negotiations on two fronts. One, they should seek liberalization by developed countries in sectors in which they have a comparative advantage. Secondly, they should seek recognition of their education, qualifications, requirements met, or licenses or certificates granted in the markets of other countries. Policy issues confronting developing countries in e-commerce are not limited to negotiating issues, however. Indeed, for most developing countries, the binding constraints on the development of e-commerce are internal.

These countries lack adequate telecommunications facilities with the density of telephone lines being less than three per one hundred people. Ecommerce can, of course, grow rapidly even when this density is low as the Indian experience testifies. But such growth is likely to be confined to an enclave and will fail to achieve its full potential. It can be argued that with superior telecommunications infrastructure and regular power supply, even Indian software exports could have grown at a much faster pace than they did. Efficiency considerations dictate that, assuming e-commerce lowers the costs of transactions; its expansion should not be confined to external trade but also extended to domestic trade. That, in turn, requires an expansion of telecommunications facilities.

Also critical to the expansion of both internal and external ecommerce are financial sector reforms. In particular, unless electronic means of payment such as credit cards are developed, the expansion of e-commerce will be slow. Electronic commerce offers unprecedented opportunities to both developing and developed countries. In the short run, the gains are likely to be concentrated in developed countries but, in the long run, developing countries have more to gain. This is because, in the short run, developing countries lack the infrastructure necessary to take full advantage of Internet. But in the long run, they can leap-frog, skipping some of the stages in the development of information technology through which developed countries have had to pass.

A paper by Suhail Ansari et.al (2000), proposed an architecture that successfully integrates data mining with an e-commerce system. The proposed architecture consists of three main components: Business Data Definition, Customer Interaction, and Analysis, which are connected using data transfer bridges. This integration effectively solves several major problems associated with horizontal data mining tools including the enormous effort required in preprocessing of the data before it can be used for mining, and making the

results of mining actionable. The tight integration between the three components of the architecture allows for automated construction of a data warehouse within the Analysis component. The shared metadata across the three components further simplifies this construction, and, coupled with the rich set of mining algorithms and analysis tools (like visualization, reporting and OLAP) also increases the efficiency of the knowledge discovery process. The tight integration and shared metadata also make it easy to deploy results, effectively closing the loop. Finally we presented several challenging problems that need to be addressed for further enhancement of this architecture.

2.5. Importance of Internet in Promoting-Commerce

The Internet allows people from all over the world to get connected inexpensively and reliably. As a technical infrastructure, it is a global collection of networks, connected to share information using a common set of protocols. Also, as a vast network of people and information, the Internet is an enabler for e-commerce as it allows businesses to showcase and sell their products and services online and gives potential customers, prospects, and business partners access to information about these businesses and their products and services that would lead to purchase.

Before the Internet was utilized for commercial purposes, companies used private networks-such as the Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) to transact business with each other. That was the early form of e-commerce. However, installing and maintaining private networks was very expensive. With the Internet, e-commerce spread rapidly because of the lower costs involved and because the Internet is based on open standards.

An intranet aids in the management of internal corporate information that may be interconnected with a company's e-commerce transactions (or transactions conducted outside the intranet). Inasmuch as the intranet allows for the instantaneous flow of internal information, vital information is simultaneously processed and matched with data flowing from external e-commerce transactions, allowing for the efficient and effective integration of the corporation's organizational processes. In this context, corporate functions, decisions and processes involving e-commerce activities are more coherent and organized.

The proliferation of intranets has caused a shift from a hierarchical command-and control organization to an information-based organization. This shift has implications for managerial responsibilities, communication and information flows, and workgroup structures.

Aside from reducing the cost of doing business, e-commerce serves as an "equalizer". It enables start-up and small- and medium-sized enterprises to reach the global market.

The Case of Amazon.com

Amazon.com is a virtual bookstore. It does not have a single square foot of bricks and mortar retail floor space. Nonetheless, Amazon.com is posting an annual sales rate of approximately 1.2 billion USD. Due to the efficiencies of selling over the web, Amazon has spent only 56 million USD on fixed assets, while B&N has spent about 118 million USD for 235 superstores. (To be fair, Amazon has yet to turn a profit, but this does not obviate the point that in many industries doing business through e-commerce is cheaper than conducting business in a traditional brick-mortar company).

Source; wiki books

However, this does not discount the point that without a good e-business strategy, ecommerce may in some cases discriminate against SMEs because it

reveals proprietary pricing information. A sound e-business plan does not totally disregard old economy values.

2.6. The Role of E-Commerce to Consumer

In C2B transactions, customers/consumers are given more influence over what and how products are made and how services are delivered, thereby broadening consumer choices. E-commerce allows for a faster and more open process, with customers having greater control. E-commerce makes information on products and the market as a whole readily available and accessible, and increases price transparency, which enables customers to make more appropriate purchasing decisions.

E-commerce makes “mass customization” possible. E-commerce applications in this area include easy-to-use ordering systems that allow customers to choose and order products according to their personal and unique specifications. For instance, a car manufacturing company with an e-commerce strategy allowing for online orders can have new cars built within a few days (instead of the several weeks it currently takes to build a new vehicle) based on customer’s specifications. This can work more effectively if a company’s manufacturing process is advanced and integrated into the ordering system.

E-commerce allows “network production.” This refers to the parceling out of the production process to contractors who are geographically dispersed but who are connected to each other via computer networks. The benefits of network production include: reduction in costs, more strategic target marketing, and the facilitation of selling add-on products, services, and new systems when they are needed. With network production, a company can assign tasks within its on-core competencies to factories all over the world that specialize in such tasks.

Elizabeth Goldsmith and Sue L.T. McGregor (2000) analyzed the impact of e-commerce on consumers, public policy, business and education. A discussion of public policy initiatives, research questions and ideas for future research are given.

Jackie Gilbert Bette Ann Stead (2001) reviewed the incredible growth of electronic commerce (e-commerce) and presented ethical issues that have emerged. Security concerns, spamming, Web sites that do not carry an "advertising" label, cyber squatters, online marketing to children, conflicts of interest, manufacturers competing with intermediaries online, and "dinosaurs" were discussed.

Mauricio S et.al, 2006, examined whether consumer perceptions of artificiality increase perceptions of e-service risk, which has been shown to hamper consumer acceptance in a variety of online settings.

Young Jun Choi and Chung Suk Suh (2005), examined the impact of the death of geographical distance brought about by e-marketplaces on market equilibrium and social welfare.

2.7. The Role of E-Commerce in Linking Stakeholders

E-commerce facilitates organizations' networks, wherein small firms depend on "partner" firms for supplies and product distribution to address customer demands more effectively.

To manage the chain of networks linking customers, workers, suppliers, distributors, and even competitors, an integrated or extended supply chain management solution is needed. Supply chain management (SCM) is defined as the supervision of materials, information, and finances as they move from supplier to manufacturer to wholesaler to retailer to consumer. It involves the

coordination and integration of these flows both within and among companies. The goal of any effective supply chain management system is timely provision of goods or services to the next link in the chain. .

Figure 2. Old Economy Relationships vs. New Economy Relationships

Source; Introduction to E-Commerce

Zhongzhou Li (2002), on his paper entitled-“Commerce Business Model”, states that the international debate about the so-called new economic paradigm seems to slowly converge on a consensus that the application of information and communication technologies will have a far-reaching impact on the growth of productivity of national economies. However, the rapid pace in the development of ICT technologies also causes alarm about a possible widening digital divide between developing and developed countries. Identifying ways in which the enterprises of developing countries can reap the benefit of the emerging e-economy, can also contribute to narrowing the global digital divide.

Judith E. Payne, E-Commerce Readiness for SMEs in Developing Countries: A Guide for Development Professionals, LearnLink1 Academy for Educational Development, 2009. The paper uses a broad definition of electronic commerce, including the use of ICT in any way that improves a SME’s relationships with customers or suppliers. This includes actually transacting business electronically — orders, invoices, shipment documents – as well as using ICT for marketing, market research, customer service, finding potential customers

and suppliers, offering entirely new products and services and more. These changes may mean more international business, but not necessarily. It may be easier and make much more sense to focus on domestic markets.

The paper addresses each of the constraints and suggests ways to adapt an e-readiness initiative accordingly. Development professionals may want to focus on a particular context, e.g., sector, for e-readiness training, building on an area's strengths. For example, tourism or textile manufacturing may be good candidates for specific areas and are both industries where electronic commerce is having dramatic effects.

2.8. E-Commerce in Ethiopia

It is clear that the development of e-commerce has greatly facilitated business transactions globally. Although, e-commerce activities are expanding in the world, its applications in Ethiopia are yet to come. Both the development of the ICT industry and the use of ICTs in business transactions by firms are still inadequate. However, in spite of the lack of conducive e-commerce environment, both technical and institutional, there are a few companies in Ethiopia that have been attempting to trade goods and services using electronic payment systems and technologies through the internet; for example, Ethiolink, Genuine Leather. In addition, there are a few attempts to promote the development of the ICT industry itself.

Ethiopian Information Communication Technology Development Agency (EICTDA) has conducted a survey on promoting electronic commerce for development in Ethiopia and explored the issues, challenges and road map. Situational analysis was conducted to examine what is needed to implant e-commerce in the country. In addition EICTDA also conducted a project on a road map towards development of e-commerce standards in Ethiopia in

collaboration with E-Systems Africa and Netwise. The study recommended the need to set standards to join e-commerce and things that are needed to implement e-commerce.

However e-commerce has tremendous opportunity to the country. The presence of large number of Ethiopian Diaspora is quite an opportunity to find market overseas for import and export business, especially in its export of leather, Ethiopic craft, coffee, Ethiopic costume, and potential for tourism.

Elizabeth A. et.al. (2010), analyzed the E-Commerce Readiness in Ethiopia. The paper focuses on preparing e-Readiness guideline to Ethiopia. The e-commerce readiness in Ethiopia can be measured by developing a new model as a result of customizing the existing models, or by preparing the one that seems most suitable for Ethiopian condition.

2.9. Challenges of e-Commerce

There a number of challenges on e-commerce in the country. Lack of IT personnel, poor telecom infrastructure, not having proper ICT policy, lack of foreign currency, communication barrier due to use of local language are some of the problems that hinder the full utilization of e-commerce in Ethiopia. According to a study by International Telecommunication Unit (ITU) in June 2009, among 85 million Ethiopian population, only 360 000 have access to the Internet

Getachew Worku (2010), states that low level of internet penetration and poorly developed telecommunication infrastructure, lack of suitable legal and regulatory framework for e-commerce and e-payment, high rates of illiteracy, high cost of Internet, absence of financial networks that links different banks, lack of reliable power supply, and cyber security issues are the most important challenges for the development of e-banking in Ethiopia.

Richard Holbrooke(2003) paper analyzes the challenges of e-commerce based on Camerons e-economy and tries to see what is needed to go from e-promotion to e-commerce readiness to help Africans specially woman.

Prithviraj Dasgupta and Kasturi Sengupta (2002), examined the future and prospects of e-commerce in Indian Insurance Industry. Their findings were

- Many issues raised by the e-commerce await judicial resolution.
- The information transferred by electronic means which culminates into a contract raises many legal issues which can't be answered within the existing provisions of the contract act.

2.10. Opportunities of e-Commerce

Arvindpanagariya (2000), analyzed Economic issues raised by e-commerce for the World Trade Organization (WTO) and developing countries. E-commerce offers unprecedented opportunities to both developing and developed countries.

Ziad H et.al (2009), conducted a study on Electronic Commerce Adoption Barriers in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Developing Countries: The Case of Libya showed that that 63per cent of the business participated in his study has a web site. While only a few of the businesses do have websites that will support online shopping and 80per cent does not support online shopping, 73per cent of the businesses are planning to introduce online shopping to support in the future. Also, the outcome revealed that the majority (83per cent) of the businesses have their own access to the internet, whereas the majority of businesses surveyed are connected by leased line (49per cent), 37per cent by DSL, and 7per cent by dialup 7per cent by other means.

Mahdi Salehi and Mehrdad Alipour (2010), stated that all major banks have declared e-business as one of the core strategies for the future developments. At

the same time, e-banking acceptance depends probably on bank service quality, customer preferences and satisfaction. One of the main reasons for the growth of e-banking is that, if handled correctly, it can significantly lower the cost of delivering products and services. The results of this study showed that the customers also strongly agree with e-banking in Iran.

However, with banking customers growing increasingly comfortable with the digital lifestyle, their expectations from financial service providers have undergone a significant transformation but Iranian customers are not aware about e-banking in Iran. They did not fully understand the power of technology and seek to leverage it to enjoy better control over their banking operations. According to this condition they are in the middle of the way. Bankers and practitioners should try to introduce e-banking very well in Iran. To conclude that e-banking may also provide other benefits. For instance, creating new markets, and reducing operational costs, administrative costs and workforce are increasingly important aspects for the banks' competitiveness, and e-banking may improve these aspects as well. So, Iranian banks should take these advantages of e-banking in Iranian economics as early as possible.

Sherif Kamel and Maha Hussein (2001), in their studies on the development of e-commerce state e-commerce presents enormous potential opportunities for business and socioeconomic development. Its rapid implementation is an urgent challenge for firms, industries and governments. E-commerce represents for the developing world an opportunity to keep pace with the developed world and capitalize on the enormous resources available, making optimum use of the world's fastest growing information and communication technology on the planet, the Internet. In the light of these issues, this paper presented the concept of the Internet with reflections on the Egyptian experience, the past and the agenda for the future to promote and diffuse the electronic commerce culture in

Egypt, aiming at realizing business and socioeconomic development as we approach the twenty-first century.

Sacha Wunsch-Vincent (2003), reported that, the search for principles and rules concerning IT and ecommerce is ongoing in the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the WTO has a very important role to play in IT/e-commerce governance. The WTO's influence on these matters, however, may not be fully appreciated outside the realm of trade policy experts. The purpose of this paper is to increase not only awareness but also knowledge of the WTO's existing and potential IT/e-commerce agenda.

Although the WTO has been an important forum for discussing IT/e-commerce issues, little concrete progress has been made in the Doha negotiations on these issues. The lack of progress can be explained by many factors: the lull in negotiations after the Cancun Ministerial; failure of Doha Declaration to identify IT/e-commerce as a negotiating topic; the dispersion of IT/e-commerce issues in different WTO negotiating groups; threshold negotiating issues that pre-occupy WTO members, such as agriculture; and the relative lack of trade barriers effecting e-commerce today.

Because of the inaction on IT/e-commerce in the WTO, negotiations on this important has gravitated to preferential trade agreements. The United States, in particular, has been addressing digital trade in its bilateral and regional trade negotiations. The global nature of e-commerce flows and the increasingly globalized nature of the IT and services industries warrant a more concerted approach at the multilateral level. Moreover, there is also a symbolic value in keeping the WTO Agreements in line with the reality of international trade flows. Waiting for next global trade talks to be launched—possibly not before five or more years—is definitely not satisfactory. Moreover, it is quite certain

that the complex issues involved cannot be handled by the WTO members between rounds of global trade talks.

When this study was completed in June 2004 new signs of a possible second take-off the Doha Negotiations became visible. Ideally, this analysis of digital trade issues and the proposed solutions will succeed in putting a spotlight on electronic trade and in providing direction.

Chapter III: Research Methods

3.1 Overview

The main objective of this research is to analyze opportunities and challenges of e-commerce in general and the case of Ethiopia in particular. In order to fulfil research goals, the researcher opted to obtain the view of stake holders in the process of e-commerce. Policy makers, legal entities consumers and business people were the participants of the questionnaire. Specifically, a total of twenty respondents from Commercial Bank of Ethiopia (CBE), National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE), Ethiopian Information and Communication Technology Agency (EICTDA), business people and consumers were selected to make up the sample for each questionnaire. Selected participants answered a survey questionnaire. Data gathered from this research instrument were then computed for interpretation. Along with primary data, the researcher also made use of secondary resources in the form of published articles and literatures to support the survey results.

3.2 Research Design

The descriptive method of research was used for this study. Data was gathered about the present existing condition, describing the opportunities and challenges of e-commerce.

The researcher used this kind of research to obtain first hand data from the respondents so as to formulate rational and sound conclusions and recommendations for the study.

In order to gather relevant data, purposive sampling was used. The respondents are policy makers, business people and consumers from banks, government offices and people who have orientation towards international business in

Ethiopia. For this research, primary and secondary data were gathered. The primary data were derived from the answers the participants gave during the survey process. The secondary data on the other hand, were obtained from published documents and literatures that were relevant to explicate opportunities and challenges of e-commerce. With the use of the survey questionnaire and published literatures, this study took on the combined quantitative and qualitative approach of research. By means of employing this combined approach, the researcher was able to obtain the advantages of both approaches to overcome limitations of methods.

3.3 Participants

In order to determine the challenges and opportunities of e-commerce in the case of Ethiopia, a total of forty respondents were asked to participate. To gather pertinent data, certain inclusion criteria were imposed. The participants who were qualified for sample selection were those who were directly involved in commerce related activity especially in international business. This qualification ensured that the participants understand the nature of the questionnaire and its use for e-commerce, making the survey items easy for them to fill in. The respondents were selected from three companies, NBE, CBE, EICTDA, and from different business sectors in Ethiopia

Purposive (Judgment) sampling was used for the sample selection. This involves the choice of subjects who are most advantageously placed or in the best position to provide the information required. Could the respondents have expert knowledge by virtue of having gone through the experience and processes themselves? Since the idea of e-commerce is not in its implementation phase in the country, the few people who have exposure to international market were the ones who were chosen to give feedback on this issue.

3.4 Instruments

Survey questionnaire was used as the main data-gathering instrument for this study (See Appendix I and II). The questionnaire was divided into two: The First one was for banks, ICT Agency and telecommunication. The general concept of the questioner was to get information about the challenges and opportunities of e-commerce for the country and why the challenges were not addressed.

The second questionnaire was for business people who have know-how on international business and specific to e-commerce. The aim was to get information about their experience, do they have the interest on e-commerce and do they see a bright future on it and why it is not yet there.

3.5 Data Processing and Analysis

After collecting all the completed questionnaires from the respondents, total responses for each item were obtained and tabulated using Social Statistical package for Social Sciences software (SPSS). The responses given are presented by way of percentages and graphs. The findings from the study are presented along with a detailed analysis in the following chapter of this research project

3.6 Limitation of Judgment Sampling Method

Judgment sampling may curtail the generalizing ability of the finding due to the fact that samples of experts who were conveniently available were used. However, it is the only viable sampling method for obtaining the type of information that is required from very specific pockets of people who are very knowledgeable of the subject matter. Hence, the descriptive method used would complement the information gathered from the only available sources.

Chapter IV: Findings and Analysis

Findings and analysis on opportunities and challenges of e-commerce in general and the case of Ethiopia are presented below using both secondary data and primary data.

4.1 Opportunities of e-commerce

E-commerce offers unprecedented opportunities to both developing and developed countries. In the short run, the gains are likely to be concentrated in developed countries, which they have more to benefit. This is because, in the short run, developing countries lack the infrastructure necessary to take full advantage of Internet. For many countries, especially developing ones, most consumers do not have computers or Internet access. A likely scenario, therefore, is one in which a handful of independent entrepreneurs will receive the product by Internet, convert it into physical form such as CDs and sell the latter to consumers. However, this activity may itself be costly, using up real resources. In the long run, they can leapfrog, skipping some of the stages in the development of information technology through which developed countries have had to pass.

The development of the internet in the 20th century led to the birth of an electronic marketplace (e-marketplace), which is now a kernel of electronic commerce. An e-marketplace provides a virtual space where sellers and buyers trade with each other as in the traditional marketplace. Various kinds of economic transactions and buying and selling of goods and services, as well as exchanges of information, take place in e-marketplaces. E-marketplaces have become an alternative place for trading. Furthermore, an e-marketplace can serve as an information agent that provides buyers and sellers with information on products and other participants in the market. These features have been

reshaping the economy by affecting the behavior of buyers and sellers (indiamba.com).

The emergence of social networks and cloud computing are very good facilitators of e-commerce, thus widening the opportunities

In this project work opportunities are listed in general format because what it is offering to other parts of the world is also applicable to the case of Ethiopia.

4.1.1 Economic and Efficiency Gains of E-Commerce

While electronic commerce is a far from frictionless mode of exchange devoid of transaction costs, it offers significant cost savings both within and between firms, especially for the processing and delivery of digital products. Even for tangible goods, e-commerce can provide closer and faster links with suppliers and customers, thereby reducing costs, especially those associated with carrying inventories. Such qualities are fuelling the growth of electronic commerce (Cohen, 1998) and are especially important to wholesalers and retailers for whom the impact of even small savings on typical profit margins of 2 to 3 per cent can be large. Forrester Research estimates that e-commerce can double these margins from 2.2 to 5.6 per cent on average because of payroll reductions due to reductions in sales staff (2.4 points) and catalogue printing and shipping costs (1 point) While the profits of some wholesalers and retailers may increase, in some cases, as discussed above, their activity will be reduced or eliminated.

To obtain a rough estimate of the potential impact of cost reductions attributable to e-commerce on the economy as a whole, the methodology developed for the OECD's regulatory reform work (OECD, 1997), was used. Based on an input-output model, electronic commerce was assumed to reduce total wholesale and retail trade activity for consumer expenditures by 25 per cent. It was assumed that this reduction would lead to a decline in the use (cost) of buildings and

related services (construction, real estate and utilities) by 50 per cent, or a 12.5 per cent decline in total for retail and wholesale trade. The smaller size of the wholesale and retail sector would lead to less use of labor and capital by these sectors, both of which were assumed to decline by 30 per cent for these services, or 7.5 per cent for the total retail and wholesale sectors. The partial equilibrium resulting from these changes in costs leads to a reduction in aggregate distribution costs of about 5 per cent (United States: -5.2; Japan -5.3; Germany -5.9; France -4.2; United Kingdom -4.5) and in total economy-wide costs by about one-half to two-thirds of a percentage point (United States -0.7; Japan -0.7; Germany: -0.6; France -0.5; United Kingdom -0.6). While small, this is still a considerable gain, since a reduction in these costs is a rough proxy for productivity gains (total factor productivity – TFP) which has only averaged an annual increase of 0.8 per cent across the G7 economies in the recent past (1979-97) (OECD, 1998).

Given that the cost savings due to business-to-business e-commerce are significant and that the business-to-business segment represents a much larger portion of the overall total, these estimates based on a business-to-consumer scenario are conservative. The economy-wide savings from the substitution of e-payment systems for paper cheques in the United States are estimated at \$30 billion, and the extension of similar efficiencies to the greater economy are assumed to be “...orders of magnitude higher” (OECD, 1999).

4.1.2 Direct Export

Selecting an appropriate mode of entry into foreign markets is critical to small firms with limited resources that cannot invest in long-term risk. Indirect exporting by SMEs through exporting representatives reduces time and costs tremendously as these expenses are shared with their distribution representatives in entering and potentially expanding into new foreign markets.

Implementing ecommerce, firms can acquire information related to potential and current foreign customers, business partners, and markets, as well as competitive intelligence much more easily than in previous years and at minimal expense.

Similarly, based on transaction cost theory, in many cases firms will favor in-house management if the costs of managing business exchanges internally are lower than the costs of conducting the exchanges through the mechanism of the market. Even though costs of acquiring information required for evaluating partner performance in the foreign environment are higher than costs of obtaining the same type of information domestically, communicating, negotiating, and coordinating activities can be accomplished inexpensively, and evaluating and monitoring partner performance can be achieved more effectively through sophisticated technology including the Internet (Ali et.al, 2010).

In the case of Ethiopia, the situation is not different from the analysis given above. All the respondents agree that e-commerce will be very useful in eliminating middle men retailers in supply chain management.

4.1.3 Reporting and Goal Monitoring

Any company owner or manager knows it is essential to have real time control over all aspects of online business and that means accurate and accessible monitoring and reporting. A quality e-commerce web site software suite provides integrated, comprehensive utilities needed to make the right decisions for operating a successful e commerce website. Popular reports provided by professional e-commerce software packages include sales analysis and trends, inventory tracking, customer buying habits, accounting software interfaces, and web site statistics like search engine performance, popular pages

on your website, and of course, "which keywords are people using to find my site". In a nut shell, e commerce is able to provide one with the tools needed to run day-to-day operations from where one wants to operate.

4.1.4 Distribution

Although shipping costs can increase the cost of many products purchased via electronic commerce and add substantially to the final price, distribution costs are significantly reduced (by 50 to 90 per cent) for digital products such as financial services, software, and travel, which are important e-commerce segments. For these products, the cost reduction associated with electronic commerce could have large economic impacts and further fuel the migration of these sectors to electronic commerce. In the case of airlines, electronic tickets now account for about half of all tickets for some major carriers; this has resulted in substantial savings and is forcing competitors to follow suit. For sectors such as music, where songs can be downloaded directly from the producer, or news, where the journalist e-mails the reader directly, huge savings are reaped over traditional forms of distribution. This reduction in distribution costs is especially important for international trade, as the ability to “download” some products without incurring shipping costs is thought to be a strong stimulus to trade, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Even for tangible goods, e-commerce methods can reduce the administrative costs associated with trade and customs clearance by over 25 per cent (WTO, 1998).

4.1.5 Changing the Cost Structure of the Value-added Chain

Just as electronic commerce reduces the internal costs of many transactions; it also changes the cost structure that dictates a firm’s relationships with other businesses. This set of relationships is called the value-added chain, the network

of upstream and downstream businesses, from raw materials to final sale, through which a product travels. At every stage of processing, an intermediary often performs a service which facilitates this flow – adding value but also adding cost. In many cases, this service is information intensive – matching a buyer to a seller, certifying parties in a transaction, providing support for the transaction (for example financial or legal services) – and often involves some type of risk sharing. Electronic commerce, especially in intangible products, may reduce the involvement of intermediaries in the value added chain and thus lower costs.

4.1.6 Market Entry

Changes in firms' relative cost structure affect the competitiveness of existing firms and their incentives to enter new markets. Anecdotal evidence suggests that barriers to entering various product markets and international markets have declined and that some characteristics of e-commerce may favor small businesses over large. In terms of stimulating competition, one of the most important opportunities of e-commerce has been the emergence of new entrants in product markets where Internet e-commerce has dramatically changed the sector's competitive dynamics. While many observers point to the Internet booksellers' success in forcing their "bricks-and-mortar" competition to come on line and match their price discounts, the largest competitive challenge has probably come from new entrants that provide digital services at a much lower cost than traditional suppliers.

The early stage of electronic commerce makes predictions based on the current situation difficult, but, for some segments of the e-commerce market, small start-ups unencumbered by existing relationships with traditional retail outlets or a large sales force may be at an advantage. In these cases, entrants can adopt a business model that forces larger, established competitors to "cannibalize"

their existing relationships or be seen as non-competitive. Examples of this phenomenon include Sony's decision to bypass its traditional retailers and sell music directly or GM's GMBuyPower.com Web site, which "... reduces dealers to little more than test drive centers and distribution points".

While it is typical for smaller firms to lag behind larger firms in their adoption of ICT, an Industry Canada/Statistics Canada survey found that expense was the most important factor delaying the implementation of e-commerce by small firms, and that lack of skills and the complexity of e-commerce were ranked as much less important (Industry Canada, 1997). However, as the cost of implementing e-commerce falls and as the benefits become more widely known, small firms' entry will be more pronounced. This is already the case in the United States where "... companies less intimidated to jump in are the smaller ones because they have less to lose, a lot of Gen Xers with some smart ideas" (OECD, 1999).

4.1.7 E-commerce integration

Zabihollah Rezaee, Kenneth R. Lambert and W. Ken Harmon (2006), reported that the rationale for infusion of e-commerce education into all business courses is that technological developments are significantly affecting all aspects of today's business. An e-commerce dimension can be added to the business curriculum by integrating e-commerce topics into existing upper-level business courses. Students would be introduced to e-commerce education and topics covered in a variety of business courses in different disciplines for example, accounting, economics, finance, marketing, management and management information systems.

E-Commerce will also assist in promoting trade among African regions as member will be able to transact their business on line. This will significantly

reduce the cost of doing business physically. This will also assist in reducing time of doing business among member states. As eluded to earlier, e-commerce in Ethiopia is not very develop. This has significantly impacted on trade facilitation within cities and regions within the country.

4.1.8 E-Commerce and E-Insurance

The recent growth of Internet infrastructure and introduction of economic reforms in the insurance sector have opened up the monopolistic Indian insurance market to competition from foreign alliances. Although the focus of e-commerce has been mainly on business to consumer (B2C) applications, the emphasis is now shifting towards business to business (B2B) applications. The insurance industry provides an appropriate model that combines both B2C and B2B applications.

Traditional insurance requires a certificate for every policy issued by the insurance company. However, paper certificates encumber problems including loss, duplication and forging of the certificate. The conventional certificate is now replaced with an electronic certificate that can be digitally signed by both the insurer and the insurance company and verified by a certifying authority.

Online policy purchase is faster, more user-friendly and definitely more secure than the traditional processes and it is, therefore, more attractive to the insurer. At the same time it incurs less cost and requires fewer resources than traditional insurance and is therefore more profitable for the insurance company.

E-insurance also makes the insurance procedure more secure since the policy details are stored digitally and all transactions are made over secure channels. These channels provide additional market penetration that is absent in traditional channels and help in earning more revenue than traditional insurance processes.

4.1.9 Future Media of E-Commerce

There will be wider range of relevant media, including interactive digital TV, and a range of mobile and wireless services. Patric Barwise (2001), reported that 99 per cent of e-commerce today is done using PCs either desktops or laptops. For B2B e-commerce this is unlikely to change. For B2C e-commerce however, things will be more complex.

There will be huge difference between different consumers' ownership of equipment and access technology. Some will have broad band access and others have no digital communication at all. The situation in Ethiopia is different mainly due to lack of adequate use of e-commerce due to poor infrastructure development in this area.

All the above mentioned opportunities of e-commerce can be summarized in the following graph on doing business online

Figure 3. Impact of Doing Business Online

Source: <http://www.pide.org.pk/pdf/psde%2018AGM/E-Commerce%20&%20WTO.pdf>

From the graph above, the result reveals that e-commerce will bring about several opportunities. According to this graph, the highest opportunity is recorded in customer service and internal processes.

4.1.10 The case of Ethiopia

The opportunity mentioned on the general case also applies to the case of Ethiopia. Result from questionnaire summarized in the following table

Table 3: Opportunities of e-Commerce the case of Ethiopia

Opportunities of e-commerce	Number of Respondents
Strengths the economic well being of the country	15
Integrates Ethiopia to the world market	15
New market creation	12
Regulation of market structure (it will avoid middle layers seller or buyer)	10
Transparency country level transparency will increase	8
Leads to formal account transaction high cost of transaction will decrease	5
Better banking service which will increase the deposited capacity	6
Higher exchange rate due to flexibility of the services	8
Convenience	15
Physical cash challenges resolved	8
Number of customers handled at a time will grow	12
Business to business will grow	8
Government to business will be improved like e-procurement	5
Export will be facilitated	13

Out sourcing will be facilitated due to cheap labor	8
Societal awareness will increase	15

Source: Questionnaire

Ethiopia is known for exporting coffee, livestock, gold, leather products, *khat* and oil seeds. In terms of world livestock production, Ethiopia holds the tenth position. A major portion of the livestock production is exported to neighboring countries. The country is exporting raw leather as well as luxury leather-made products. Floriculture is also expected to rise in the near future due to massive investment in the sector.

As can be seen from the table majority of respondents agreed that e-commerce will open new market for the country and strengths the country's economy.

E-Commerce will significantly play a key role in facilitating trade, particularly in the above mentioned products, where Ethiopia has a comparative advantage.

4.2 Challenges of e-Commerce

E-commerce is a smokeless business. However, there are constraints associated in making transactions electronically. Physical delivery of products bought electronically takes time and costs money. Not only delivery is costly but also there is uncertainty regarding quality, as one cannot see the products physically and as well as the legality of the company, by which there is no guarantee of money before delivery of goods. In addition to these, there are issues regarding privacy and security of electronic transactions. Whether or not payment details (for example. credit card details) will be misused is also a big concern.

Companies and individuals are using computer networks to conduct increasing amounts of their daily business. For instance web search engines auctioned some \$10 billion of ad space in 2007, accounting for almost half of all online advertising revenue. Sales at Amazon.com were \$4.13 billion in the first quarter of 2008, including a fast-growing revenue stream from selling Web services to

other e-commerce companies. At eBay, sales reached \$15.7 billion in the second quarter, with 84.5 million active users. This explosion of large-scale e-commerce poses new computational challenges that stem from the need to understand incentives. Individuals and organizations that own and operate networked computers and systems are autonomous, they will generally act to maximize their own self-interest—a notion that is absent from traditional algorithm design (Indianmba.com).

Challenges of e-commerce differs from developed countries to African countries, here the paper will try to state the challenges in terms of general challenges, African challenges and finally challenges of e-commerce in Ethiopia

4.2.1 General Challenges

4.2.1.1 Security and Privacy

Research in security and privacy has been a central theme in academic computer science for more than 30 years. Although many clever algorithms, protocols, and devices have been rigorously analyzed, experimentally deployed, and even commercially developed, few of these solutions are in widespread use.

In 2001, Anderson initiated a new security-research direction by questioning the tacit assumption that security is primarily a technical problem. “Information insecurity is at least as much as due to perverse incentives” as to technological failure, he said. “Many of the problems can be explained more clearly and convincingly using the language of microeconomics: network externalities, asymmetric information, moral hazard, adverse selection, liability dumping, and the tragedy of the commons.” In the years since Anderson’s seminal paper appeared, most aspects of security and privacy research have been suffused with economic considerations.

The increase in e-commerce has coincided with an erosion of consumer privacy seems paradoxical. After all, the ability to shop without having to stand face-to-face with others in a store seems privacy enhancing. Encryption, pseudonyms, electronic cash, and numerous other techniques purport to enable online consumers to protect their personal information and their identities.

In practice, however, the trend has been for online merchants to ask for more information about their customers and for customers, even sophisticated ones who claim to value privacy, to provide this information when asked. Acquits offers the following explanation: “Behind privacy intrusion there is often an economic trade-off. Individuals want to avoid the misuse of the information they pass along to others, but they also want to share enough information to achieve satisfactory interactions; organizations want to know more about the parties with which they interact, but they do not want to alienate them with policies deemed as intrusive.” Behavioral economics combined with experimental psychology yields the following general explanation for privacy erosion. Even “sophisticated” consumers who value privacy will often compromise it to improve their position in an ongoing transaction. They know that loss of control over their private information poses a long-term threat, but they cannot assess the long term risk accurately enough to compare it to the short-term gain in the ongoing transaction.

Although not strictly an “e-commerce” issue, privacy in public databases is relevant to this discussion. In publicly available, sanitized aggregations of sensitive data about individuals, the canonical example of which is a census database, there is a natural tension between *utility* of the collection and *privacy* of the individuals, and communities often opt for utility. Among all forms of unwanted communication, email spam has received the most attention. However, the phenomenon also includes link spam (which degrades search quality), shilling (which degrades reviewer and recommender systems), and

click fraud. Given this rogue's gallery, there is widespread agreement that the incentive structure of next-generation network services must be designed more carefully. Techniques for incentive-based prevention of unwanted communication include pricing via processing, attention bonds, and click-based learning algorithms. Now here is the inadequacy of a purely technical approach to information security clearer than in the realm of copyright enforcement.

Digital-content distributors do have some control over the prices of their products and the flexibility with which purchased products can be used (for example, the extent to which they can be copied, shared, or modified), but although more flexible products may fetch higher prices they may also show dampened sales. Taking into account the fact that some digital environments are highly permeable, Bergmann et al. show the following: If users are homogenous, there is a critical permeability level up to which all users buy the product, and the optimal price and flexibility levels decrease as permeability increases. When permeability rises above the critical value, the number of users who buy decreases, and the optimal price and flexibility stay constant. A platform vendor who also sells digital content (which he licenses from copyright owners) will find it optimal to allow very flexible use by platform customers and to set a low price for content; most of the vendor's profit is from platform sales. Copyright owners' revenue is low, because prices are low and sharing of content is common. Tension between the platform vendor and copyright owner is observed in the real world. In 2005, the *Financial Times* quoted a music executive as saying, "Our music is not something to be given away to sell iPods."

Other issues: Manufacturers competing with intermediaries online "Disintermediation" - a means of eliminating the intermediary such as retailers, wholesalers, outside sales reps by setting up a Website to sell directly to customers. Disintermediation include

- i. music being downloaded directly from producers; and
- ii. Authors distributing their work from their own Web sites or through writer co-operatives.

4.2.1.2 Risk in e-service Encounters

Mauricio S. Featherman, Joseph S. Valacich & John D. Wells(2006), reported that as companies race to digitize physical-based service processes repackaging them as online e-services, it becomes increasingly important to understand how consumers perceive the digitized e-service alternative. E-service replacements may seem unfamiliar, artificial and non-authentic in comparison to traditional service processing methods. Consumers may believe that new internet-based processing methods expose them to new potential risks the dangers of online fraud , identity theft and phishing swindles , which are schemes to steal confidential information using spoofed web sites, have become commonplace, and are likely to cause alarm and fear within consumers.

4.2.1.3 Legal Issues/ Contracts

Beside many advantages offered by the IT, a number of challenges have been posed to the legal system. The information transferred by electronic means which culminates into a contract raises many legal issues which cannot be answered within the existing provisions of the contract act. The IT act does not form a complete code for the electronic contracts.

Farooq Ahmed(2001) reported that some of the multifaceted issues raised are summarized in the following manner.

- a. Formation of e-contracts
 - Contracts by e-data interchange
 - Cyber contracts

- b. Validity of e-transactions.
- c. Dichotomy of offer and invitation to treat.
- d. Communication of offer and acceptance
- e. Mistake in e-commerce
 - Mutual mistake
 - Unilateral mistake
- f. Jurisdiction: cyber space transactions know no national and international boundaries and are not analogous to 3- dimensional world in which common law principles involved.
- g. Identity of parties

The issues of jurisdiction, applicable law and enforcement of the judgments are not confined to only national boundaries. The problems raised are global in nature and need global resolution.

4.2.1.4 Human Skills Required for E-Commerce

It's not just about E-commerce; it's about redefining business models, reinventing business processes, changing corporate cultures, and raising relationships with customers and suppliers to unprecedented levels of intimacy.

Internet-enabled electronic commerce: web site development, web server technologies, security, integration with existing applications and processes. Developing electronic commerce solutions successfully across an organization means building reliable, scalable systems for

- i. Security,
- ii. E- commerce payments
- iii. Supply- chain management
- iv. Sales force, data warehousing, customer relations

- v. Integrating all of this existing back-end operation.

Source: www.wto.org

4.2.1.5 Socio-Cultural Factors

Societies in developing countries are cash-based. They prefer and trust traditional payment systems and are less likely to adopt new technologies. This has been also the case of Ethiopia. New technologies will not dominate the market until customers are confident that their privacy will be protected and adequate assurance of security is guaranteed. Low literacy rates, along with low per capita income and low electricity consumption, and limited mobility, hinder internet access or use. Many African countries have less than 50 per cent rate of literacy. The rates are particularly very low in rural areas and low literacy rates mean less internet use.

Information in local language enables efficient and desirable use of PCs and internet. Providing computers to schools and developing School Net programs may not be sufficient in areas where the major international languages (for example, English, French, and Spanish) are not spoken or used. Accessing the internet can be helpful if contents are developed in local languages.

The General challenges can be summarized in the following chart as Yousouf put it on a paper e-commerce and WTO.

Figure 4. Obstacles in Doing Business over the Internet

Source: <http://www.pide.org.pk/pdf/psde%2018AGM/E-Commerce%20&%20WTO.pdf>

From the graph, privacy and security is the major obstacle of doing business, followed by three others, namely, inadequate legal protection; face to face customer interaction; and costs of implementing sites. Cost of internet access appears to pose less challenge. However, in many developing countries, the cost of internet access is high and impacted heavily on the implementation of e-commerce activities.

4.2.2 Challenge Facing Africa

Although a number of e-commerce activities are emerging in most African countries, its growth has been slow for a variety of reasons, including low levels of Internet penetration and limited communication infrastructure. Many Africans are still unaware of the opportunities offered by e-commerce.

The African private sector consists mostly of small, medium, and micro-sized enterprises (SMEs) and the informal sector. These businesses are widely seen as a potential engine of growth in the information economy. E-commerce offers huge potential to SMEs, including potential strategic benefits such as possibilities of creating new industries, developing new content and chances to find or create employment.

However, companies and the private sector in Africa have not been active initiators of e-commerce. For example, a survey in Ghana (part of a Ghana SCAN-ICT study) revealed that about 65 per cent of ICT companies do not have a presence on the Internet and 84 per cent reported that they were not involved in e-commerce. In Morocco, according to the Ministry of Industry, Trade and Telecommunications, the proportion of businesses that use the Internet grew from 20 per cent to 42 per cent in 1999 but only 8 per cent of businesses in all sectors currently use the Internet for placing orders online. A similar study on Mozambique shows that e-commerce and e-business do not formally exist in Mozambique.

The major obstacles include lack of suitable legal framework and security instruments, inadequate banking systems, poorly developed telecommunications infrastructure, especially beyond urban areas, and high rates of illiteracy. Twenty companies out of sixty six surveyed in Mozambique have websites and this low proportion by world standards was considered a barrier for e-commerce and e-business development.

Much still needs to be done to encourage e-commerce in Africa. Key steps include the rapid development of human resources, greater attention paid to e-literacy among citizens and activities to build capacity, particularly to provide a skills base among SMEs for e-commerce. Governments should encourage business start-ups and incubation projects that advance this activity, including

through public-private partnerships, and to pay particular attention to getting women engaged in e-enterprises.

A new form of e-commerce, which follows the rapid growth of wireless technologies, is mobile commerce (m-commerce), which is likely to have significant impact in Africa. M-commerce is the buying and selling of goods and services using mobile telephones or personal digital assistants (PDAs). It can also be used for the main types of e-commerce – B2B, B2C, B2G and C2C. Many African societies predominantly use cash for transactions, because of their mixture of formal and non-formal economies, and this provides the basis for a surge of m-commerce in Africa, especially for SMEs in rural and remote areas. Approximately 0.03 per cent of Africans own bank accounts, compared to 6 per cent of Africans who have a mobile telephone.

The Internet is the driving force for the growth of ecommerce. This means that Africa’s growth potential is limited by the lack of infrastructure (connectivity) and equipment. The number of Internet subscribers grew by 2,357.3 per cent from 2000-2010 in African countries see table 4 for details.

Table 4: Internet Users and Population Statistic for Africa

INTERNET USERS AND POPULATION STATISTICS FOR AFRICA						
African Region	Population (2010 Est.)	Population percentage in World (%)	Internet Users, Latest Data	Penetration (% Population)	Use Growth (2000-2010)	per cent Users in World
Total for Africa	1,013,779,050	14.8	110,931,700	10.9 per cent	2,357.3 %	5.6 %
Rest of World	5,831,830,910	85.2	1,855,583,116	31.8 per cent	420.5 %	94.4 %
World Total	6,845,609,960	100.0	1,966,514,816	28.7 per cent	444.6 %	100.0 %

Source: <http://www.internetworldstats.com>

An added advantage is that there is a growing convergence of Internet and mobile communication and handsets have acquired functionalities that only a few years ago could only be found on personal computers.

4.2.2.1 Policy Approaches

Monopoly provision of telecommunication access and weak regulation results in high costs of service and limited business opportunities for value-added services.

In the study of the ECA/IDRC in 2000-1, it was found that businesses and others in the North African countries of Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia were increasing adopting ecommerce. The report notes: “All three countries have recognized the important role of government in setting up the conditions within which e-commerce can be developed, and appear to be moving both to amend necessary legislation and provide a demonstration effect by launching pilot projects”.

The same survey covered three countries in Southern Africa (Mozambique, Namibia and South Africa) and found that e-commerce had a “high profile only in South Africa. South Africa’s Green Paper on e-commerce provides thoroughly solutions to the challenges facing many African countries, on the implementation of e-commerce. (Aida et.al. 2003)

Table 5. Five Countries with Strong e-Commerce Legislation

E-commerce Legislation, Regulations and Policy	
Country	Law No. 15/2004 on E-signature and Establishment of the information Technology Industry Development Authority (ITIDA).
Mauritius	The Electronic Transactions Act 2000,

	(August 2000)
Morocco	Comite Interministeriel pour le Development et la Promotion du Commerce Electronique, which has also produced a preliminary report.
South Africa	Electronic Communications and Transactions Act [No. 25 of 2002]
Tunisia	Electronic Exchanges and Electronic Commerce Law [enacted in August 2000]

Tunisia tops the African developing countries in ICT development and competitiveness, and has been exporting software and IT services since 1999. This is according to the World Economic Forum's Networked Readiness Index of 104 countries, published in March 2005. This is attributed to improving in the regulatory framework, infrastructure, business and development support, and education. Egypt, through the Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT), has also developed an enabling environment and infrastructure. This includes encouraging the creation of new firms based on new technology products and services, improving the skills of the workforce, using electronic documents and developing an infrastructure for making e-payments. One undertaking is a legislation project for e-business, addressing issues such as e-payment, e-contracting, customs and taxation, and "cyber" crimes committed on the Internet or by computer. Egypt has also prepared a law permitting electronic signatures, to facilitate Government and business use of electronic documents.

Through the assistance of ECA in supporting national e-strategies via the National Information and Communication Infrastructure (NICI) plans, other countries are beginning to recognize the importance of the sector. For instance, Burundi, Comoros, Cameroon, Gambia, Ghana, Mali and Tanzania have

outlined plans to develop e-commerce through sectors (“NICI Pillars”) as described in the table below:

Table 6: NICI Policy Statement on E-commerce ; African Countries

Country	NICI Policy Statement on e commerce
	Trade and industry - One of the activities listed in the priority sector of trade and industry is the promotion of e-commerce.
Comoros	Improving the legal and regulatory environment, adopting laws and other regulations is a strategic pillar, and will concentrate on the areas including intellectual property, management of the .km Internet domain for facilitating e-commerce, and other Internet-based activities.
Cameroon	E-commerce is listed as one of the priority sectors of the Cameroon NICI policy document.
Gambia	Trade and commerce: Specific objectives under this priority area of the draft NICI policy and plans for The Gambia include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To develop virtual operating companies and e-merchants accounts; • To facilitate the immediate launching of e-banking and an electronic payment system in the country in collaboration with the banking institutions; • To design and facilitate appropriate ICT training programs geared towards developing e-commerce competence at both business and technical levels; • -To encourage Internet and e-commerce activities to support the tourism industry.
Mali	Trade, industry and services: Objectives of this sectoral application of the Mali NICI policy are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Utilizing ICTs to collect, verify and diffuse information in the area of trade, industry and services; • Promoting the creation of ICT industries;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting the development of electronic commerce and e-business.
Ghana	<p>Developing a globally competitive value-added services sector, a regional business service and ICT hub to encourage and facilitate the use of open electronic marketplaces, secure e-business solutions, electronic signatures, electronic public procurement and electronic payment systems to support the development of electronic commerce in the country.</p>
Tanzania	<p>Service sector: The policy objectives, challenges and policy statements of the service sector in the Tanzanian National</p> <p>Information and Communications Technologies policy include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishing an environment conducive for e-commerce transactions and competition; Encouraging more usage of ICT in financial services (banking, insurance, etc); Promoting the use of ICT to enhance efficiency, effectiveness and continuity in the provision of services and basic utilities, especially in billing and payment systems; Developing and deploying a nationwide e-Tourism system.

Source: Aida et al., 2003

Besides all this initiatives by few African countries the majority of them do not have a proper policy regarding this issue. One key reason for the slow development of e-commerce in Africa is that there is no overall policy framework (with the exception of the five countries mentioned) covering aspects such as technical, economic and political aspects. Policy considerations when creating an enabling environment include:

- i. **Encryption** and decryption techniques provide authentication, authorization, confidentiality and integrity to services, increasing the security of ecommerce transactions. They are necessary, for instance, for processing credit card information;

- ii. **Digital signatures and electronic contracts** are relevant, for instance in cases of dispute between trading partners in an e-commerce transaction;
- iii. **Certification authorities** secure electronic transactions and act as trusted third parties to verify information about parties. African certification authorities must take part in the international framework for supporting ways to link certification mechanisms and the mutual recognition of different certification authorities;
- iv. **Consumer protection:** In an electronic market place it is not easy for consumers to identify and localize suppliers so it is necessary to promote protection mechanisms;
- v. **Electronic payments:** Online payment using credit cards is a missing component of the African business environment, which is often cash-based. Electronic payments will involve central banks and other trade and financial institutions; and
- vi. **Copyright and intellectual property rights:** Legislation on copyright and intellectual property rights on the Internet is still in its infancy, and uncertainty about such legislation contributes to inhibiting business investment. (Aida et.al.,2003
- vii. **Financial environment:** credit cards are taken for granted in the developed world and are the sine qua non for B2C e-commerce. Also, e-entrepreneurs can often look to vibrant venture capital sector to fund new ventures. These are fundamental gaps in most developing countries. Many developing economies are almost entirely cash-based. Credit cards are virtually non-existent, and central bank clearing facilities are very limited. Concerted collaborative efforts between fiscal authorities, banks and private sector merchants will be needed to create an e-commerce friendly financial environment. A sea change in banking attitudes will be needed to enable a venture capital market.

4. 2.2.2 The Information Infrastructure

Whether e-commerce relates to physical goods or tele-services, the costs of equipment and connectivity loom large in developing countries, especially in monopolistic regimes. Limited bandwidth adds to the problem of providing off-line tele-services and online tele-services demand high quality fast network access. There is need for developing countries to invest more in information infrastructure in order to address some of the challenges of the e-commerce. Countries should include e-commerce policies into their national strategy

4. 2.2.3 Transportation and Delivery Systems

Perhaps nowhere is the contrast between developed and developing countries more vivid than here. The essence of B2C ecommerce is instant gratification! The placing is instant gratification! The placing of an instant order (and perhaps the equally quick debiting of the consumer's account) has to be followed up with appropriately quick delivery of the goods. While this is eminently feasible for virtual goods such as music files, it is far from so when it comes to physical goods. Airfreight is risky, infrequent and expensive in Africa; customs clearance procedures are long and complex; local warehousing facilities hardly exist.

4. 2.2.4 Human Capacity

The people required to effect e-commerce have to be computer literate, oriented towards the digital economy, and comfortable with the major languages of the Web. Those that meet the requirements have to be willing to stay in their home countries and not join the brain drain. Countries need to engage their people in training of e-commerce.

4.3 The Case of Ethiopia

Ethiopia still has a highly regulated telecommunications infrastructure. There is only one state-controlled Internet Service Provider (ISP) – The Ethiopian Telecommunication Commission (ETC). Ethiopia, compared with other African countries, has a large and affluent Diasporas and a number of them are entrepreneurs who are engaged in selling various unique Ethiopian-content products online.

Items being advertised on the foreign-based Ethiopian websites market include Ethiopian art, music, designs, Geez Font software and others. Their websites are mostly found in Canada and the United States. In addition to the websites, some of the newspapers now have online versions attracting large visitor ratings from Ethiopians living abroad wanting to know what is happening at home (for example, www.addistribune.com). The Ethiopian Diaspora, therefore, provides a market for small Ethiopian business-to-consumer sites.

Despite regulatory and infrastructure problems, there are a few Ethiopian companies identified as e-commerce operations. A poor banking infrastructure, the absence of credit cards and stringent exchange control regulations are significant barriers to development, both restricting the growth of those e-commerce ventures currently operating and turning away possible foreign investment in new initiatives.

Ethiopia like any other developing countries faces a number of challenges in implementing e-commerce. The major challenges companies face include unreliable, continuously failing and costly internet connection; shallow user base; lack of awareness by customers and the business community; absence of adequate banking infrastructure; and unsupportive postal services. The connection problem seems to be one of the major bottlenecks in the

development of e-commerce in Ethiopia. The companies which are using e-commerce reported that there is a big challenge pertaining to access and reliability of internet services, and there is persistent connection failure.

The difficulty of customers in using/ finding the company's website is another serious constraint faced by many people as well as companies. There is need for the responsible body of the government to assist them in their attempt to introduce and expand business over the internet, which is a common practice in other countries. The support could come in the form of revising the commercial code such that it recognizes and supports e-commerce activities; improving the speed, cost and availability of the internet services; devising an easy mechanism to get an internet merchant account; providing a workable e-banking and postal service; availing financial incentives in the form of tax holiday, duty exemption and so on; and creating awareness among the masses.

Slow development of towns and cities also contribute significantly to the slow progress of e-commerce in Ethiopia. All e-commerce companies are located in Addis Ababa, despite the large populations being living in some rural areas. This is comprehensible given the fact that banking and logistical services are more developed in Addis than in other cities and towns. This shows the need to build up facilities in other cities in order to expand and promote e-commerce activities beyond the metropolis. Challenges of e-commerce can be categorized in five major groups in addition to what is mentioned in general challenges of e-commerce that of African.

4.3.1 Electronic Commerce Policy and Strategy

According to the Sustainable Development and Poverty Reduction Program (SDPRP), ICT is taken as across cutting issue in all of the four building blocks. Realization of the importance of ICT and ICT policy has been put in place and a

full-fledged ICT Authority called the Ethiopian Information Communication Technology Development Authority (EICTDA) to handle all issues related to ICT policy. The major components of the ICT policy include ICT human resource development, establishment of a government information network, content and application development and community based information systems and services.

In spite of the positive considerations given to the ICT sector, the issue of e-commerce was not raised explicitly in the SDPRP. In addition, while there has been major expansion in telecommunications coverage during the SDPRP period there has not been sufficient commitment towards reducing the cost of ICT access in terms of taxes and tariffs.

Although no concrete emphasis has been given to the issue of e-commerce, it can be assumed that any e-commerce initiatives could easily be implemented if the necessary regulatory frameworks are put in place in addition to the infrastructural expansion. The plan also has stressed that the technical capacity of the regulators should be strengthened. Legal and administrative frameworks for information security, privacy protection, records management, business process outsourcing, and standardization will be developed during the plan period.

4.3.2 Human Resource Development

Given the low levels of development in ICT, the skills barrier will continue to be a major challenge in Ethiopia due to lack of advanced information society skills. Educational institutions are prompt at picking up the demand of the society and enterprises; however, most of the teaching still focuses on the basics than the actual skills to compete in the globalized market. Hardly has any educational institution established close links with companies in equipping

students for business needs. Enterprises have not taken initiatives in specifying their requirements in the short and medium run, so that educational institutions can develop their teaching plan accordingly.

The increasing number of students however, was not able to scale up due to inadequate capacity, significant mobility and brain drain. The teaching and learning process in computing and engineering field is primarily focused on producing teachers and middle level programmers and engineers that cater for the small and medium business involved in hardware and software sales, support, training, and network services along with a few systems integrators and software developers. Most importantly the brain drain is high and Ethiopia is unable to cope with the critical mass needed for promoting social and economic development and mobility of its work force in this area.

4.3.3 Core Legal Framework for e-Commerce

Generally, E-commerce over the world raises so many legal issues such as legal validity, certainty, uses trust, security and dispute settlement mechanisms. The development and innovation of technology that has brought in the application of Information and Communication Technologies in the world is also greatly impacting Ethiopia.

The basic commercial and civil laws in Ethiopia which were drawn in the 19th century are mainly based on paper methods of transactions. This situation also exists in a number of countries as highlighted by Professor Christopher Reed, who argued that the laws in most countries were developed over a long time during which physical actors and physical media were the only, or at least the primary, mechanisms by which transaction with legal consequences could be affected. The laws and regulations were designed to facilitate paper-based transactions that are not in line with the current advanced technological changes

with legal rules that require the use of documents, written notices and manuscript signatures.

Most laws such as civil laws and contract laws that regulate transactions require an agreement to be made authenticated in writing and signed by the person who is to be bound by it. These are the key legal issues under the current legal system that will obviously not be desirable under e-commerce and electronic transactions. Indeed the based methods of transactions requirements can pose an obstacle to the development of e-commerce at national, regional and international level (Adam, 2010).

4.3.4 Electronic Payment Systems and Logistics

A well functioning electronic payment system is critical to the advancement of electronic commerce. Ethiopian banking sector is far behind the rest of the world in facilitating online electronic payments. A series of financial sector reforms has been introduced since 1994, when private banks were allowed to be re-established. Cash is still the most dominant medium of exchange and electronic payment systems are at an embryonic stage. Credit cards are not issued by local cards due to the risks involved and foreign currency restrictions.

Despite some initiatives to improve online access to customers, most banks still operation dependent of each other. Inter-bank settlement is done manually. Currently, checks of private banks can only be settled through the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia. In an effort to enable automatic settlement of checks from different banks for small amounts and enabling inter-bank gross money transfers, the National Bank of Ethiopia has launched an automatic transfer system based on the real time gross payment settlement and Automatic Clearing House (ACH) systems. The ACH establishes a clearinghouse that would allow

settlement of all checks and money transfers from different banks at a central clearinghouse.

4.3.5 Telecommunication Infrastructure and Cost

While the cost of Internet access has been revised down ward in recent years the cost of broadband network is high compared to the rest of the world that have direct impact on the way Internet is developed and used. A 1 Mbps DSL access was costing about US\$3000 per month in 2006. The broadband prices were revised downwards in May 2009 where DSL prices were cut between 30 to 75per cent depending on the speed. The price of 1 Mbps DSL connection was revised downwards by 75per cent to US\$820. The ITU report of 2010 estimates monthly subscription of broadband is US\$486.51 which is \$ 1'739.27 when adjusted.

The high broadband cost means entry to electronic commerce will be difficult in Ethiopia compared to the developed countries. Other costs include high start-up investment costs, high costs of computers and telecommunication and licensing requirements. (E-Systems Africa and Netwise, 2010).

As a world bank report shows from the year 1995 to 2008 Ethiopian internet users number is rapidly growing, see the graph below

Figure 5. Ethiopian internet user's growth
Source: world Bank, world development indicators

Ethiopia has the lowest overall tele density in Africa. The population is approaching 90 million, but there are less than 1 million fixed lines in service, and a little more than 3.3 million mobile subscribers. The number of internet users is dismal below 500,000 at the end of 2009; 450,400 internet users as of Jun 2010, 0.5 per cent of the population, per ITU. (<http://www.eastafricaforum.net>)

Apart from the high cost low quality services, Ethiopian consumers face the following challenges

- Inadequate and low levels of messaging and information distribution infrastructure to facilitate consumer driven electronic commerce such as mobile banking and mobile commerce. This was exacerbated by disruption of Short Messaging Service (SMS) and lack of an interface; and

- Low levels of online publishing and hosting services in the country. There are few websites that promote the marketing of goods and services in Ethiopia.

Summary of challenge of e-commerce in Ethiopia from the questioner is presented below in the graph

Figure 6. Summary of Challenges of e-Commerce in Ethiopia
Source: Questionnaire

From the graph above, infrastructure, legal, and policy are the three major obstacles to the implementation of e-commerce in Ethiopia. According to the survey, standards poses limited challenges to the e-commerce.

4.4 Initiatives in Promoting e-commerce in Ethiopia

E-payment: The Banking sector recognizes its key role in facilitating online payments. Efforts are underway to introduce ATM machines by almost all Banks. Dashen Bank is the most advanced with over 55 ATM terminals in its area branches, university compounds, shopping malls, restaurants and hotels along with over 500 Point of Sale terminals at major commercial

establishments. Dashen Bank is a principal member Visa and Master Card. Services provided by Dashen Bank ATMs include cash withdrawal, balance Inquiry, mini-statement, fund transfer between accounts attached to a single card and PIN (Personal Identification Number) change.

Dashen Bank has signed an agreement with iVeri, a South African electronic payment technology company, for the introduction of mobile commerce in April 21, 2009. According to the agreement, iVeri Payment Technologies has licensed its Gateway and MiCard epayment processing solution to Dashen Bank. This would make Dashen Bank the first bank in Ethiopia to acquire e-commerce and mobile merchant transactions. Dashen has implemented i-very payment gateway, but it has not been made active.

The United Bank is the first bank to introduce tele-banking - including text messages (SMS) by the end of 2008. Zemen Bank and Wogagen Bank has followed suit in 2009 with the introduction of ATMs at major branches in Addis Ababa. Zemen Bank is the most advanced with regards to online banking. Customers can check their balance over the Internet. Zemen Bank allows online money transfer between different accounts of a same client, although it does not support transfers between different client accounts as yet.

The largest state-owned bank, Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, is the pioneer in introducing ATM service for local users in 2001 with its fleet of eight ATMs located in Addis Ababa. Moreover, CBE has had Visa membership since November 14, 2005. However, the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia has not been that aggressive in introducing electronic commerce due to lack of appropriate infrastructure and skills. In 2009, the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia has launched a new project to install over 250 ATM terminals in its branches and convenient locations along with over 500 Point of Sale (POS) Terminals that have access to its network.

Other banks in the pipeline include the Awash Bank, Nib International Bank and United Bank that have agreed to launch 140 interconnected ATMs between them with over 340 POS terminals throughout the country. All the banks use the Society for Worldwide Inter-bank Financial Telecommunication (SWIFT) settles their foreign transaction payments. In Ethiopia there are three agents of Western Union, the world's largest money transfer network: these are the Commercial Bank of Ethiopia, Construction and Business Bank, and Dashen Bank. Unlike SWIFT, which is used to transfer money from Ethiopia abroad and vice versa, Western Union is used to transfer money from abroad to Ethiopia only. The regulations do not allow for Ethiopian to transfer funds to foreign countries, since individuals are not allowed to hold foreign currency account in domestic banks, if they have not lived abroad or studied abroad. Exporters can hold their earning in foreign currency retention accounts. The options include:

- 10per cent - money earned in foreign currency can be kept indefinitely in the foreign currency account
- 90per cent of the transaction amount - the money can be used for importing items

The Automatic Transfer System (ATS) project of the National Bank of Ethiopia (NBE) was expected to be operational in 2010 and to facilitate fast online settlement between banks. The fund for the project was obtained from the World Bank, which requires the NBE to start the project before June 30, 2010. Consequently, all banks are required to implement core banking system before June 30, 2010 in anticipation of the completion of the ATS project.

The exchange market is at early stages in Ethiopia. The Ethiopian Commodity Exchange (ECX) project that was established two years ago is taking step for building a nascent stock market in the country. ECX has setup a framework and

a regulation that lets businesses to register and bid for purchase of agricultural commodities such as coffee, sesame, maize, etc. through ECX's system. All trading of coffee should be done and so forth through ECX. In this system, farmers deposit their commodities in ECX's warehouses, buyers deposit money in ECX's account, ECX provides a platform for bidding and ensures that the trade between buyers and sellers takes place without fraud and transfer of money from the buyers account to that of the sellers. ECX has started an initiative to automate the process, which would enable online bidding for commodities.

Moreover, a study conducted by Ethiopian Bankers Association shows that recognizing the importance of improving the National payment System; the NBE has started taking steps to strengthen the institutional framework for the payment and settlement systems in the country. Accordingly, strategic vision and plan document was drafted which showed overall direction of the countries payment system reform and modernization projects.

Human capacity development: The number of ICT students has increased significantly both in public and private institutions in recent years. According to Ministry of Education , the number o undergraduate students in ICT related fields (Computer science, Information systems and Electrical Engineering) was about 8,246 in 2006 that is 13per cent of the total enrolment in the same year.

Policy: the most recent policy framework for the next five years, spanning from 2005-2010, is the Plan for Accelerated and Sustainable Development to End Poverty (PASDEP). The PASDEP represents the second phase of the PRSP process that began under the Sustainable Development and Poverty Reduction Program (SDPRP). The PASDEP carries forward important strategic directions pursued under the SDPRP – related to human development, rural development, food security, and capacity-building (Mulat et. Al, 2008)

The PASDEP recognizes that exploiting information technology is central in order to promote growth and reduce poverty. Accordingly, it attaches high priority to “leap frog” forward the ICT sector by building a major ICT backbone and providing affordable local level access to ICT. Various targets that will enable a world class backbone and connectivity network have been set. Five major undertakings are planned with regard to the ICT sector development in the PASDEP document:

- Promoting human resource development,
- Mainstreaming the use of ICT in all sectors of the economy, in the administration of government, and in the educational system,
- Developing the necessary telecommunications infrastructure,
- Promoting research and development through ICT, and
- Creating enabling a legal and regulatory framework.

Telecommunication infrastructure: by 2014 the number of fixed line subscribers in Ethiopia is expected to increase to 4.4 million, representing an annual average growth rate of 38per cent p.a. The number of mobile subscribers is expected to grow at 43per cent per year over the period, reaching almost 20 million by 2014. The number of internet users will jump to 12 million, but internet subscribers will still be low at 1.4 million at the end of 2014. (<http://www.eastafricaforum.net>).

In addition e-commerce needs to have a reliable and secure communication infrastructure to provide sustainable customer services. The Ethiopian Telecommunication Corporation (ETC) is the sole data communication service provider in the country. Currently, ETC is working on the project of Next Generation Network (NGN). In principle, any telecom company should have alternative (backup) link to be used in the case of the main one fail. If the NGN

project does not provide any alternative link in the different circuit, the Ethiopian Bankers Association should get a permission to have its own communication link from any capable private company (Melaku et. Al, 2010).

Chapter V: Conclusion and Recommendation

This study focused on the opportunities and challenges of e-commerce in general and the case of Ethiopia in particular. Primary and secondary resources were used in the study. For the primary data, the researcher opted to conduct a survey using judgmental sampling. A questionnaire was used for data gathering. Secondary data were collected from various publications including books, journals and Internet. These were integrated to support the findings.

The Findings of this project shows that e-commerce has numerous opportunities. Opportunities identified in this paper include: increased customer services; increased sales in a number of companies; improved competitiveness among buyers and sellers; increased productivities as result of high sales, among others.

E-commerce will assist in improving the exports of Ethiopia products, including: coffee, livestock, gold, leather products, *khat* and oil seeds. In terms of world livestock production, Ethiopia is ranked tenth position in world. A major portion of the livestock production is exported to neighboring countries. The country is exporting raw leather as well as luxury leather-made products. According to the findings, Floriculture is also expected to rise in the near future due to massive investment in the sector. If the growth in floriculture sustains, Ethiopia can become one of the largest exporter of flowers and plants in the world. To facilitate this export business e-commerce plays a vital role. The country will have also a chance to sell finished products not only raw materials.

Through wide efficiency gains e-commerce was assumed to reduce total wholesale and retail trade activity for consumer expenditures by 25 per cent. It was assumed that this reduction would lead to a decline in the use (cost) of buildings and related services (construction, real estate and utilities) by 50 per

cent, or a 12.5 per cent decline in total for retail and wholesale trade. The smaller size of the wholesale and retail sector would lead to less use of labor and capital by these sectors, both of which were assumed to decline by 30 per cent for these services, or 7.5 per cent for the total retail and wholesale sectors. The partial equilibrium resulting from these changes in costs leads to a reduction in aggregate distribution costs of about 5 per cent

Despite these opportunities, the paper also highlighted some challenges of e-commerce . These include 1 identified include: low levels of Internet penetration and limited communication infrastructure, low level of human capacity, no legal background towards electronic document and settlement of legal issues, and absence of e-commerce policy and public awareness. The Government need to come up with sound policies aimed at addressing these challenges. The papers also reveals that implementation and operation of e-commerce initiatives could be accelerated if there are modern banking and insurance firms operating, and these do not exist in some African countries including in Ethiopia. It is also important to raise awareness and to offer training programs that target the business community in particular and the public in general.

According to the papers, the number of internet users in Ethiopia is estimated to jump to 12, million, but internet subscribers will still be low, 1.4 million at the end of 2014. Ethiopian Electronic Commerce Proclamation is already prepared and it is expected to be functional. The Ethiopian Bankers Association is working towards improving payment systems. National Switch System in Ethiopia' conducted study and assumed that there will be a chance to have e-payment system in the country.

More need to be done in order to address accelerate the implementation of e-commerce in Ethiopia. Of particular importance are:

- Increase the human resource development particularly in the area of ICT,
- Implement what is in progress in terms of standards, policy and electronic law
- The need to mainstreaming the use of ICT in all sectors of the economy, in the administration of government, and in the educational system,
- Improvement in the developing the necessary telecommunications infrastructure,
- Promoting research and development through ICT,
- Creating enabling a legal and regulatory framework,
- Extra source of internet connection will be recommended to provide a sustainable service and
- E-payment also should be functional
- Improve transportation system and cost
- Proper addressing of business areas, individual homes

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Annex I : Questioner for Policy makers

- 1. Is e-commerce functional in Ethiopia?**
 - a. Yes**
 - b. No**
- 2. If yes how long has it been there?**
- 3. If the answer is no for Question 1, why?**

- 4. Does Ethiopia have a policy regarding e-commerce?**
 - a. Yes**
 - b. No**
- 5. If yes, when was it approved and its legislation number**

- 6. If no, is there any plan to state a policy regarding e-commerce?**

- 7. What will do you think will be the challenges of e-commerce to be implemented in Ethiopia?**

- 8. What kind of opportunity do you think e-commerce will brought to Ethiopia?**

- 9. According to you how is e-commerce helpful to the consumer in the e-business domain?**
 - a. Broadens consumer choice
 - b. Encourages price transparency
 - c. Fastens business process

d. Do not know/ Cannot say

10. Do you agree that e-commerce as commercial means has its advantages over the traditional commercial methods?

- a. Agree
- b. Disagree
- c. Do not know/ Cannot say

11. Please state what advantages if you agree and Why if you don't agree?

12. Do you agree that e-commerce can provide an alternative marketing channel by eliminating middleman?

- a. Agree
- b. No
- c. Do not know/ Cannot say

13. For how many years you are using e-commerce?

- a. Less than one year
- b. One year -<five year
- c. More than five year
- d. Do not know/ Cannot say

14. What according to you is the future of e-commerce in Ethiopia?

- a. Very good
- b. Good
- c. Not so good
- d. Do not have a future in Ethiopia
- e. Do not know/ Cannot say

15. Do you think that e-commerce will be valuable to Ethiopia?

- a. Yes
- b. No

For Bank

16. Is online transaction allowed in Ethiopia?

- a. Yes b. no

17. Why online payment (e-payment) is not available in Ethiopia?

18. What could be the challenges and disadvantages of online payment in Ethiopia?

19. What will be the opportunities and advantages of online payment in Ethiopia?

For Telecommunication

20. Does Ethiopia have the technological infrastructure to support e-commerce?

21. What is needed to improve it?

Annex II: Questioner for Business people and Consumers

1. For how many years you are using e-commerce?

- (i) Less than one year
- (ii) One year -<five year
- (iii) More than five year
- (iv) Do not know/ Cannot say

2. For what purpose do you use e-commerce?

- (i) For personal use
- (ii) For business use
- (iii) For both personal and business use

3. According to you how is e-commerce helpful to the consumer in the e-business domain?

- (i) Broadens consumer choice
- (ii) Encourages price transparency
- (iii) Fastens business process
- (iv) Do not know/ Cannot say

4. According to you how e-commerce is helpful for the business discourse?

- (i) Effectively caters to customers' demands
- (ii) Smoothens business by creating customer and businessman network
- (iii) Ensures guarantee of payment
- (iv) Do not know/ Cannot say

5. Do you think that the application of e-commerce has increased over the years in Ethiopia?

- (i) Yes
- (ii) No

(iii) Do not know/ Cannot say

6. Do you agree that e-commerce as commercial means has its advantages over the traditional commercial methods?

(i) Agree

(ii) Disagree

(iii) Do not know/ Cannot say

7. Do you agree that e-commerce can provide an alternative marketing channel by eliminating middleman?

(i) Agree

(ii) No

(iii) Do not know/ Cannot say

8. What are the challenges to the implementation of e-commerce in Ethiopia?

(i). Slow penetration of internet

(ii). Security concerns

(iii). Lack of trust

(iv). Consumers' awareness level is low

(v). Other factors

9. What measure would you recommend for promotion of e-commerce in Ethiopia?

(i). Promotion of internet

(ii). To increase the awareness level of people

(iii). An integrated promotional approach

(iv). Other measures

10. What according to you is the future of e-commerce in Ethiopia?

(i). Very good

- (ii). Good
- (iii). Not so good
- (iv). Do not have a future in Ethiopia
- (v). Do not know/ Cannot say

11. Do you think that e-commerce will be valuable to Ethiopia?

- a. Yes
- b. No

12. Why? (Whatever answer you have for question 11.)